

D2.2 - Report on assessment of processes flexibility

WP 2, T 2.2

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Executive summary

This document contains the deliverable “D2.2 – Report on assessment of processes flexibility” of the eLITHE project (project reference: 101138325).

The objective of this deliverable is to analyse the thermal process of the three eLITHE industries from an energy perspective, focusing on the current non-electric demands per ton of output: ceramic frits, building bricks and alumina. A reference product and kiln for the current thermal processes (frits melting, brick firing and alumina calcination), heavily based on natural gas burning, are chosen to characterise energy consumption and establish a comparative baseline to evaluate the new electrified eLITHE processes. In parallel, a methodology to identify and assess energy flexibility sources, such as process planning, energy carrier or energy storage, is proposed and applied to each current thermal process. This flexibility potential is assessed and quantified wherever possible and intends to serve as a guideline for the Decision Support System (DSS) to be created within eLITHE, which will support the elicitation and delivery of electricity flexibility, both implicitly and explicitly. Due to product quality constraints, process flexibility has little margin to play with. However, there is significant potential in energy storage and the hybrid use of simultaneous energy carriers.

In addition, an economic assessment of process electrification has been done in a variety of scenarios of the current energy markets to find the boundaries of electrification feasibility and compare it with the current situation in the industry. Three economic parameters were assessed: electricity price, gas price and carbon emission charges. The best solutions for PV+Thermal Storage (TES) and PV+ Battery Storage (BES) were then selected and analysed referring to different energy market scenarios (costs of gas, electricity and carbon taxes). TES integration appears to be a more feasible solution, whereas BES have a much higher CAPEX (capital expenses) than TES, and paybacks above 10 years. Thus, integration with PV and TES appears to be the most promising solution for achieving economically viable electrified processes in the near future.

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ACRONYM LIST

Table 1: Acronym List

Acronym	Definition
Al	Aluminium
BES	Battery Energy Storage
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
EH	Electric Heating
EU	European Union
EOH	Equivalent Operating Hours
GHI	Global Horizontal Irradiance
IZF	Institut für Ziegel-forschung Essen e.V. (Brick and Tile Research Institute Essen regd.)
JRC	Joint Research Center
LCOE	Levelised cost of Energy
LCOH	Levelised cost of Heating
NG	Natural Gas
OPEX	Operation Expenditure
PBP	Payback Period
PMV	Measurement and Verification Protocol
PV	Photovoltaic
PVGIS	Photovoltaic Geographic Information System
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SGA	Standard Grade Alumina
SoC	State of Charge
TCID	Torrecid
TES	Thermal Energy Storage

ToU	Time of Use
TpD	Tons per Day
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
t	Ton (metric) or tonne

1 Objectives and scope

eLITHE's Deliverable D2.2 focuses on the energy characterization of the industrial demo processes for a standard reference product. The assessment encompasses the thermal processes of frits melting, alumina calcination and bricks firing. Currently, all processes run on natural gas as the main energy carrier. The objective of the eLITHE project is not only to optimise energy use in the thermal processes, but also to electrify totally or partially the thermal treatment, thus contributing to the decarbonisation of energy-intensive industries currently reliant on fossil fuels. Electrification also enables smarter energy management and control strategies, facilitating the use of the possible demand flexibility for both grid congestion and balancing services, and internally adapting energy demand profiles to match the most economic generation and availability profiles.

Task T2.2 delves into a deep understanding of the current processes, products and the quality and process constraints that must be respected to meet demanding market standards. In this sense, the task objectives are twofold:

- Describe the thermal processes, boundary conditions and quality restrictions and create an energy model as a baseline for comparison with future project breakthroughs and developments. This baseline is determined for a reference standard product, manufactured using reference conventional equipment only. Eventual comparisons alongside the project must adhere to the chosen reference product for which the baselines have been created. These baselines per reference process enable a fair and accurate assessment of the new processes compared to the standard current processes.
- Design an energy flexibility audit methodology and apply it to the different demonstration industries, searching for possible current and potential sources of demand flexibility. This demand flexibility is intended to be exploited in the redesigned processes, aided by eLITHE's decision support tools, in either way: internally, by shifting loads to high-availability periods and benefiting from market Time of Use (ToU) tariffs, or externally, by participating in explicit demand response schemes triggered by a grid operator during short, scheduled events for upwards flexibility (energy reduction) or downwards flexibility (energy increase).

Another objective of the task is to conduct an economic assessment of the current cost of the energy carriers, energy supply contracting issues and how energy prices affect industrial process under different remuneration scenarios. This analysis helps identify the right flexibility sources, either existing or to be deployed in the redesigned processes in front of the current energy market perspective.

The scope of the analysis is restricted to the thermal processes and do not include other industrial manufacturing activities or ancillary service equipment, such as raw material handling, compressed air, oxygen production, final product handling and packaging, etc.

The analysis focuses solely on energy, leaving other commodities and demands aside (water, raw materials, other inputs, etc.).

The document is structured into three main sections. The first section is devoted to the energy characterization of the current thermal process according to a methodological approach based on standard energy audit procedures applied to the eLITHE targets. In this section the reference product, equipment and process are described along with the control parameters used by the industries to ensure quality compliance. The second section proposes a flexibility audit methodology and describes the results of this flexibility audit per demonstration industry. The third section carries out an analysis of current and future energy prices under different scenarios to quantify the benefits of demand flexibility in each case.

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2 Energy characterization and baselining of the current processes

2.1 Energy characterization methodology

The assessment of energy demand and usage in this task is restricted to the pure thermal processes of the three eLITHE demonstrators to create the reference product. The reference product is a common average product that will be used for the demonstration activities and testing along the eLITHE project. The three thermal process under analysis are described thoroughly in the following sections, and they are:

- Frits melting in oxi-combustion gas furnaces.
- Brick firing in a tunnel kiln with gas burners to ensure a given temperature profile and dwelling time.
- Alumina calciner running on gas.

The objective of the energy characterization is to develop simple mathematical models to predict the energy consumption per unit of reference product for each of the processes. These models will be used to evaluate the impact of the new eLITHE processes in terms of energy per energy source and energy carrier, and serve as an energy baseline throughout the project.

A secondary objective is to familiarize with the product quality requirements and process limitations that the new development should comply with.

The methodology for characterizing energy demand in the thermal processes of industries heavily relies on the profound knowledge of industry experts regarding production processes. Involving these experts in discussions was key to executing the energy characterization in the three industries. In the task period between month one and month six of the project, no less than three workshops and discussions were held between CIRCE researchers and the companies' technical experts. There was no need of onsite measurements for energy characterization as the industries had plenty of historical data on energy consumption at furnaces and kilns.

The steps followed at each demo site characterization have been the following:

- **Definition of objectives and scope.** Due to the wide variety of equipment and products it was important to nail down the analysis to a specific and representative case that would stand as a reference for future comparative analysis. In this phase it was important to define the reference equipment and reference product that are to be characterized from an energy point of view and be used along the project as a comparison baseline. The product was selected by each company representative following the premises of being a common, usual and representative product of the company's portfolio, with average energy demand and standard processes. The equipment selected (furnace) is the usual one utilised for the production of the

reference product and assigned by the demonstration partner to the testing activities in ELITHE.

- **Product and process acquaintances.** A process flowchart was contributed illustrating the equipment used, the process steps, the process control parameters, the raw materials and the output in terms of products and subproducts. This flowchart became the discussion starting point for the auditing team to start identifying the key information and build the data request template tailored to every different process.
- **Energy and process related information request.** A data gathering template was designed for every process requesting historical data and encompassing several process and corporate domains.
 - **General company data:** Activity, location, employees, schedules, organization and dependencies. This data includes contact information for key personnel involved in the audit such as production and maintenance responsible staff and technical staff, as well as product quality experts and equipment experts.
 - **Overall Annual Production and Production rates.** A year of historical production records was requested, broken down by year, month and hour. Subproducts and wastes are also requested.
 - **Energy carriers and historical data.** A year of historical data was requested for each energy carrier involved in the thermal process, usually gas and sometimes electricity. In the case of energy generation assets owned by the company, the annual generation and the self-consumption rates are also requested.
 - **Energy tariffs and hourly costs.** Most industries have special energy tariffs for gas and electricity which are treated as restricted confidential information. In such cases, generic market prices or average energy price values are considered for the economic assessment of energy costs.
 - **Parameters under control.** The production parameters that affect quality, productivity and energy consumption are requested, such as raw material humidity, process temperature and pressure or throughput. Among these parameters, it was explicitly requested to list those that are used for process control such as the raw material feeding speed, the chart speed, the dwelling time, the amount of gas in the burners or the amount of oxygen in the combustion mix.
 - **Ancillary equipment related to the thermal process and energy consumption.** This may include cooling and ventilation energy, oxygen production energy, compressed air. These energy demands are only relevant if a variation may be expected derived from the process redesign intended in the ELITHE project. Otherwise, the values have not been considered for the sake of simplicity.
 - **Other relevant data according to process flowchart.** The data collection templates were shared with industrial partners to check for inconsistencies and potential data unavailability before they were asked to complete them.

- **Analysis of the data collected.** The objective of this phase was to understand thoroughly the energy drivers of each process and the parameters to monitor and control for an efficient energy management and to comply with the productivity and quality requirements of the products. The energy baselines were then constructed. During this phase many questions arose for the auditing team that require several iterations asking for clarification, additional information and debating with industry technical experts as reported in the subsequent sections.
- **Presentation of results and energy models.** The proposed energy baselines were presented and agreed with industrial partners while the necessary corrections and improvements were implemented in the final versions. These baselines are only valid for the reference products and equipment considered in the scope, but are always a good reference value to compare against along the project testing of the new redesigned processes and equipment.

The process is summarised in the following chart. In the next sections we analyse how this generic methodology was applied to each particular case and what the results are for the current thermal processes prior to the application of the intended ELITHE breakthroughs.

Figure 1. Energy characterization methodology flow chart.

2.2 Frits melting

Audit Targets

The ceramic plant pilot is run by Torrecid (TCID), a company specialized in ceramic products and located in Alcora, Castellón. Their main product is ceramic frits. This type of conventional smelting uses a continuous furnace operating at approximately 1550 °C, producing frits for ceramic applications with a production capacity ranging from 800 to 1000 kg/h per smelter.

Product & Process

The reference product for energy characterization is a commercial frit that melts at temperatures between 1540 °C and 1560 °C. The ceramic frit manufacturing process is a complex system that begins with the input of raw materials, which are mixed and fed into the smelter for melting at high temperatures. This furnace can operate in two different ways: with gas and air, or with gas and oxygen. When using gas and air, approximately 1,200 m³/h of combustion air is required, which is preheated to between 600 °C and 800 °C via a heat exchanger. This heat exchanger utilizes an energy recovery system installed in the exhaust gas pipe before the filtering stage. When gas and oxygen are used, the amount of oxygen needed varies between 200 and 250 m³/h.

The exhaust gases generated in the process are handled at a flow rate of 1900 Nm³/h. Due to the high temperature of these gases, large heat exchangers are employed to recover energy and cool the gases before they pass through filters that cool the fumes and collect the dust resulting from combustion. This system not only improves the energy efficiency of the process but also reduces environmental impact by properly managing combustion by-products.

The raw materials are mixed in a feed hopper and transported to the frit furnace using compressed air. During ignition, it is estimated that 20% of the materials are lost. In the continuous manufacturing process, the raw materials are melted at temperatures ranging from 1500 °C to 1580 °C, depending on the materials used. Once melted, the frit is extracted from the furnace by overflow. This process is applicable to most frits, although specific types have melting points ranging from 1100 °C to 1550 °C. To avoid cross-contamination, each type of frit is manufactured in separate furnaces.

The cooling of the molten frit is carried out through a water quenching process, where the frit is cooled down before packaging. This rapid cooling prevents the formation of large crystals, ensuring the quality of the final product. Additionally, at the furnace exit, a gas and oxygen burner is used to heat the frits and prevent them from solidifying prematurely.

Finally, after the cooling process, the frit is dried in a frit drier to remove residual moisture, resulting in the dry powder or frit fragments that will be used in the production of ceramic glazes and coatings. This process is crucial in the ceramic industry, as the frit, when re-melted during the glazing process, forms a vitreous layer on the surface of ceramic products, providing them with finish and protection.

Figure 2. Material flow in a conventional frit furnace.

Data collection template

A data collection template was designed to collect key historical information related to energy and production processes. This template asks for general data on the company, including its activity, products and a diagram or explanation of the process. In addition, production, by-product and waste data were collected, along with energy information, including electrical, thermal and other sources. If the company has energy generation assets, information on annual generation and self-consumption was required. Information on energy tariffs and hourly costs was also requested, along with production parameters affecting quality, productivity and energy consumption. Details were also collected on the energy consumption of auxiliary equipment related to the thermal process, together with other relevant data according to the process flow diagram.

This data is used in the flexibility audit of this document, specifically in section 3, where all this information is detailed.

Data Analysis

In the case of TCID, a specifically developed formula was designed to calculate the baseline, based on critical data obtained through an exhaustive demonstration process. This formula comprehensively incorporates a series of key variables that are essential for the precise evaluation of energy performance. Among the data considered are detailed electricity and gas consumption, production volumes associated with different stages of the process, as well as product variations throughout the process. The systematic integration of these variables into the formula ensures a highly accurate and reliable baseline estimate, which will serve as an essential reference for assessing energy performance under various operating conditions. This baseline not only facilitates the comparison of current

performance with expected outcomes but also enables the identification of potential areas for improvement in energy efficiency over time.

Results

The established baseline has become an essential reference point for evaluating the energy performance of the process. This reference allows for measuring energy performance at a specific moment and making consistent comparisons over time.

To develop this baseline, it was necessary to gather and analyse various key data. First, energy consumption was recorded during a representative period, including both total consumption and specific consumption in different stages of the process. This energy data was combined with detailed information on production, encompassing the total production volume (measured in tons) and variations in the product mix during the period under study. The analysis of this data made enabled the identification of energy consumption patterns related to different production levels and changes in the product mix. As a result, two fundamental formulas were defined to evaluate energy performance:

Table 2: Frits melting baseline

	Baseline	Other information
Average specific demand on annual basis	Demand (P)= 2340*t	t = tons in the period 2340 = Specific energy consumption for the reference frit (kWh/t)
Specific demand + batch change energy demand	Demand (P)= Start up energy + production energy = 13104*x + 2301.4*t	X = product mix changes in the period 13104 = Energy consumption needed at the beginning of a new frit production batch in the reference furnace (kWh per recipe change) 2301.4 = calculated average, excluding production mix changes (kWh/t)

These formulas reflect how energy demand relates to production volume and the complexity of the product mix. The established baseline allows not only the measurement of current performance but also the projection and comparison of future energy consumption based on different operational scenarios, which is essential for more efficient long-term energy planning and management.

eLITHE project:

In the eLITHE project, a new frit smelter for ceramic applications is planned, utilizing electric resistive heaters and induction technologies. The prototype electric smelter will be a 200 kg/h batch furnace featuring 1000 kW electric power. The raw materials will be fed into the furnace from the top using a screw feeder.

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Once the materials reach a liquid state, a combination of resistive heaters and induction coils will provide the necessary heating energy. The induction coils will be positioned at the outlet of the furnace.

The new furnace will be constructed using refractory materials that require cooling during the process to preserve their working properties. The cooling system will be designed with a water flow at the bottom of the furnace, necessitating additional water consumption for this purpose. Since the new process is electric there is no need of an exhaust heat recovery system. The produced frit will be analysed to ensure it meets the initial specifications. The chemical composition will be characterized by XRF, and the physicochemical properties will be measured using hot-stage microscopy. Additionally, the ceramic performance will be evaluated.

To evaluate the energy consumption in each of the demos, a baseline calculation has been conducted. This process aims to identify and estimate the expected energy consumption by taking into account a series of relevant variables that influence energy behavior. The baseline not only provides a reference point for comparing the actual energy performance of the demos but also helps detect potential deviations and areas for improvement. In this way, a more accurate and context-specific evaluation of energy consumption is ensured, based on the specific conditions of each demo.

Figure 3. Material flow in the proposed new electrical furnace

2.3 Brick firing

Audit Targets

The demonstration case is led by the Brick and Tile Research Institute Essen (IZF) in Essen, Germany. This demonstration focuses on the construction brick and tile production sector, aiming to implement a hybrid electric - Hydrogen heating system in existing tunnel kilns for brick firing, reaching temperatures of up to 1000 °C.

Product & Process

The reference product chosen for eLITHE is the perforated brick with 2.79 kg/unit of weight. Every kiln cart carries 2688 pieces with a total weight of 7.5 t. The total company annual

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production is approximately 120,888 tonnes per year along 90% of the year (337 working days/year).

Figure 4. Perforated brick taken as reference product for the project eLITHE. [Source: IZF]

The current full brick manufacturing process is illustrated in the following figure, which highlights four well-defined and distinct stages.

Figure 5. Full brick manufacturing flowchart. [Source: IZF]

The process begins with the preparation stage, where raw materials are handled. This step starts with the feeder, which introduces the raw materials into the production line. Next, the materials pass through a grinding mill, where they are crushed to achieve a finer consistency. Then, the crushed material is directed to a rolling mill, which further adjusts the thickness and consistency of the material. The preparation stage ends in the souring house, where the material is conditioned or stored before moving on to the next phase. This entire stage primarily relies on electricity.

Once the preparation is complete, the process moves to the shaping stage, in which the material is given shape. Here, the material is processed through an extruding press, which molds it into a continuous profile. Then, a cutter divides this profile into specific-sized pieces. In some cases, such as in the production of roof tiles, a revolver press is used to give the product additional shape and detail. This stage also uses electricity as the main energy source.

After moulding, the shaped product enters the drying stage. The material is placed in a drying chamber, where moisture is removed at a temperature of approximately 100°C. This stage ensures that the material is ready for firing. Drying is done using a combination of natural gas and electricity. It also takes some thermal energy transferred from the firing stage.

The firing stage is the most energy-intensive and is the focus of this characterization. Here, the dried material is introduced into a tunnel or roller kiln, where it is fired at extremely high temperatures, ranging from 900°C to 1200°C. This firing is essential to harden the material and give it its final properties such as durability. Firing primarily relies on natural gas to generate the necessary heat, although some electricity is also used.

During the process, waste heat is generated in the firing stage. This waste heat is recovered and reused in other parts of the process such as drying, contributing to overall energy efficiency.

Heating and cooling temperature profiles are critical to ensure material properties and produce seamless product pieces. Kiln cart speed, gas combustion and cold air intake are controlled to ensure the correct temperature profile as shown in the following schematic chart. The temperatures are for reference and do not necessarily match with those needed for the reference product.

Figure 6. Material and gas flow temperature profiles along the firing process .[Source: IZF].

Preheating: In this first stage, the products enter the kiln and begin to heat up gradually. The temperature increases as they advance toward the firing zone. In the graph, this phase is represented by the initial upward slope of the temperature curves. Preheating allows the material to reach the appropriate temperature before it undergoes high-temperature firing.

Firing: This is the central stage of the process, where the products reach the highest temperatures, typically between 900°C and 1450°C, depending on the type of product and specific requirements. The burners located at the top of the kiln (depicted in red at the top of the image) provide the necessary heat for this stage. The red curve in the graph

represents the temperature of the gas, which is higher than the temperature of the solid (black curve) due to the burners. This stage is crucial for imparting the final strength and durability to the material.

Rapid Cooling: After firing, the products go through rapid cooling. In this phase, the material's temperature drops quickly, as shown by the steep decline of the curves in the graph. This cooling is achieved by introducing fresh air (represented by the blue arrows at the top of the image).

Static and Final Cooling: In the final stages of the process, the products undergo a more controlled and gradual cooling. The graph shows how the temperature continues to decrease, although at a slower rate compared to rapid cooling. This part of the cooling process is crucial to ensure that no cracks or deformations occur. The goal is for the products to reach a temperature of around 573°C before the final cooling.

Temperature Control: The temperature of both the gas and the solid is carefully regulated throughout the process to ensure that the products are uniformly fired and achieve the desired physical properties.

Data collection template

A data collection template was designed to gather key historical information related to energy and production processes in the context of brick manufacturing. This template requests general company data, including its activity, products, and a diagram or explanation of the process. Additionally, production data, by-products, and waste were collected, as well as energy information, including electrical, thermal, and other sources. If the company has energy generation assets, information on annual generation and self-consumption was required. Information on energy tariffs and hourly costs was also requested, along with production parameters that affect quality, productivity, and energy consumption. Details on the energy consumption of auxiliary equipment related to the thermal process were also gathered, along with other relevant data according to the process flowchart.

This data is utilized in the flexibility audit of this document, specifically in section 3, where all this information is detailed.

Data Analysis

In this case, the baseline has been specifically calculated taking into account the particularities of the brick production process. Our analysis has focused on the thermal process in the tunnel kiln. For this phase, energy consumption is exclusively on natural gas, so electricity consumption has not been considered in the baseline calculation. As in previous cases, brick production in tonnes, is the key independent variable that directly influences the energy demand.

Results

The overall energy consumption of the brick manufacturing industries in Germany, is 5.4 TWh per year. Of this total, 89% comes from natural gas, which is the predominant source

of energy, especially during the firing phase. The remaining 11% comes from electricity, mainly used in the preparation, moulding and drying phases.

Following the same methodology used in previous installations, a new baseline calculation has been carried out, taking into account the production as key variable. This process allows to obtain an accurate estimate of the energy required to produce a specific number of tons of bricks.

To perform this analysis, it was essential to collect data on the specific energy consumption in each phase of the manufacturing process. The firing phase, being highly dependent on natural gas, was identified as the stage with the highest energy demand. In contrast, the preparation, moulding, and drying phases, though less energy-intensive, rely heavily on electricity, providing us with a clear view of how energy consumption is distributed throughout the process.

Table 3: Bricks firing baseline

		Baseline	Other information
Firing process demand	Firing Demand (kWh/t)= 158.2 * t		t = tonnes in the period
Drying process demand	Drying Demand (kWh/t) = 123 * t		t = tonnes in the period

According to literature, the total gas consumption in a brick factory is divided as 60% to tunnel kiln and 40% to dryer, close to the registered values. Since drying is not subject to changes in eLITHE, our baseline can be simplified to the firing demand. This equation reflects the direct relationship between production volume and energy consumption and , allows to estimate future energy requirements and savings deriving from any change in the process or equipment..

eLITHE project:

For this project, a large chamber kiln with a volume of 12 m³ available at IZF will be modified. This kiln will allow for the simulation and evaluation of different configurations of perforated and solid bricks, as well as roof tiles, and test radiation screens on the side walls . The longitudinal circulation of the chamber kiln makes it comparable to a section of a tunnel kiln, allowing the simulation of a section of a section of tunnel kiln.

The existing internal circulation system will be adapted to withstand temperatures of up to 900 °C, contributing to the necessary convective heat transfer. Inside the kiln, there is the internal circulation fan without housing, and the extraction system for gases and air towards the longitudinal circulation.

The main objective of this pilot project is to demonstrate the technical, environmental, and economic feasibility of a hybrid or fully electric heating system for brick firing. IZF will develop

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a model of a tunnel kiln with electricity and hybrid heating with green hydrogen burning, using a simulation tool to represent the process and test various changes. The results of these simulations will serve as the basis for constructing the demonstrator. Several hybridization options for the kiln will be considered, including electric input for preheating the combustion air. Heat transfer will be achieved through radiation screens installed in the kiln walls, while new charge structures will also be evaluated.

2.4 Alumina calciner

Audit Targets

In Greece, the Metlen's project pilot aims to revolutionize the calcination of hydrated alumina in the alumina production industry. The current approach uses vertical calciners operating at 1000 °C, fuelled by natural gas, to produce high-purity Smelter Grade Alumina (SGA) with high purity alumina (Al_2O_3) content higher than 99% as gamma and alpha – alumina. The raw material is referred as hydrated alumina, alumina tri-hydrate, aluminium hydroxide or Gibbsite ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$). This process is highly energy-intensive, requiring between 3 to 4 GJ of natural gas per ton of alumina, which results in approximately 0.2 tons of CO_2 emissions per ton of alumina.

Product & Process

Circulating Fluidised Bed Kilns and Gas Suspension Calciners are two key technologies in the calcination of materials used for alumina hydroxide. Within this demo site, these are the reference processes. In the figure 7 is represented a circulating fluid bed kiln, similar to the ones in use in Metlen calcination plant in Greece.

Figure 7. Scheme of a representative circulating fluid-bed reactor furnace for alumina

In the aluminium hydroxide calcination process, the material particles are mixed and suspended in a bed of particles that is kept in motion by injecting a high-velocity gas flow. This hot gas flow provides the energy necessary to dehydrate and calcine the material, transforming it into calcined alumina.

The process is carried out at a temperature of approximately 950°C under a pressure higher than atmospheric (>101.3 kPa). The material retention time in the reactor is between 3 to 5 minutes, allowing for uniform and controlled calcination. The material repeatedly circulates within the reactor, improving process efficiency and ensuring that all particles reach the desired temperature.

Finally, the calcined material is separated from the exhaust gases in a recycling cyclone, allowing for product recovery and emission reduction. The process is highly efficient and allows for a production capacity of up to 3500 tons per day (TPD).

An alternative to the fluid-bed reactors is the gas suspension calciners such as the one represented in the figure 8.

Figure 8. Scheme of a representative gas suspension calciner furnace for alumina

The Gas Suspension Calciner is an advanced method for the rapid calcination of aluminium hydroxide. In this process, the material particles are introduced into a stream of hot gas that suspends them in the air, allowing for rapid heat transfer and efficient calcination.

There are two main configurations for this process:

- With no Holding Vessel: Here, the material is subjected to a temperature of 1050 °C and remains in suspension for 10-12 seconds. This method is fast and allows for a high production capacity of up to 4,500 tons per day. It is ideal for processes where speed and capacity are priorities.

- With Holding Vessel: In this case, the material is subjected to lower temperatures (less than 960 °C) and remains in the furnace for 200 seconds or more, allowing for slower and more controlled calcination. The production capacity in this configuration is up to 3,500 tons per day.

Both configurations operate under pressure lower than atmospheric (<101.3 kPa) and allow for precise control of the final quality of the product. The choice between one or the other depends on specific production requirements and the properties of the material to be calcined. Metlen operates both technologies in the calcination plant in Greece.

Data collection template

A data collection template was designed to collect key historical information related to energy and production processes. This template asks for general data on the company, including its activity, products and a diagram or explanation of the process. In addition, production, by-product and waste data are collected, as well as energy information, including electrical, thermal and other sources. If the company has energy generation assets, information on annual generation and self-consumption was required. Information on energy tariffs and hourly costs was also requested, along with production parameters affecting quality, productivity and energy consumption. Details were also collected on the energy consumption of auxiliary equipment related to the thermal process, together with other relevant data according to the process flow diagram.

This data is used in the flexibility audit of this document, specifically in section 3, where all this information is detailed.

Data Analysis

In this case, the baseline has been specifically calculated taking into account the particularities of the calcined alumina production process. The analysis has been focused on the calcining kiln. At this stage, energy consumption is largely based on natural gas, but also on electricity. As in previous cases, alumina production is a key variable that directly influences the outcome of our calculation. In summary, the benchmark for calcined alumina production is based on three key variables: natural gas consumption, electricity consumption and tonnes produced.

Results

The baseline has been established on the basis of annual average values, where the total energy demand (P) for alumina calcination is calculated using the formula attached in the table 5.

The total energy demand is broken down into two key components:

- Electricity consumption: Represented by the value 28 MWh/t, this factor reflects the amount of electricity consumed per ton of calcined alumina.

- Natural gas consumption: Represented by the value 825 MWh/t, this value indicates the natural gas consumed per ton produced, which is the primary energy source in the calcination process.

Altogether, these values allow for the total energy demand to be calculated for any given level of alumina production over a given period, thus providing a baseline for analysing and optimising energy consumption in the calcination process. This baseline will be used as reference for assessing the energy efficiency of the process.

Table 4: Alumina calciner baseline

	Baseline	Other information
Specific demand based on average annual values	$\text{Demand (P) = Electricity + Gas}$ $\text{Consumption} = 28 \cdot t + 825 \cdot t$	$t = \text{tons in the period}$ $28 = \text{Electricity consumption (MWh/t)}$ $825 = \text{Gas consumption (MWh/t)}$

eLITHE project:

To reduce dependence on natural gas and minimize greenhouse gas emissions, Metlen is exploring innovative alternatives such as microwave heating. This technology heats the target material directly rather than the surrounding medium, leading to significant efficiency gains. The modular design of the system facilitates expansion by adding parallel modules, allowing flexible adjustment of new calcination plants according to production needs. Key challenges include the physicochemical specifications required for metallurgical-grade alumina, maintaining a stable and continuous process, and scaling the technology to process up to 2000 tons per day.

The demonstration will focus on implementing a fully electric microwave-based calciner capable of operating at temperatures up to 1000 °C with a total power of at least 70 kW. This new calciner will build on the advancements made in the RemovAl project, incorporating innovations such as a dynamic coupling system to adapt to dielectric variations of the material, real-time control of thermal and electromagnetic signals with automatic adjustment, and a feeding system that ensures precise residence times.

Initial tests will be conducted at CEI facilities using a 30 kW system to assess performance, characterize the thermal and electrical properties of alumina and its suitability for microwave heating, and model heat transfer and furnace performance with electric heating. The goal is to calcinate at least 10 tons of hydrated alumina during the demonstration phase, achieving an energy consumption of the calciner equal to or less than 3 GJ/t of alumina, equivalent to 833 kWh/t, in line with the current gas baseline, thus successfully validating the new technology at TRL 7. If successful, the project is expected to reduce greenhouse gas

emissions by 40% in the overall alumina production from bauxite ore, considering full-scale implementation.

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3 Energy flexibility sources and flexibility assessment

3.1 Flexibility characterization methodology introduction

The purpose of this section is to provide a methodological framework for the standardisation and deployment of energy flexibility audits in companies and industrial processes wishing to delve further into their flexibility potential and benefit economically from the adequate exploitation of demand response strategies, both for internal or external use.

A flexibility audit is a good complementary analysis of an industrial process, following an energy audit. Energy audits are already a common practice in companies, and notably in those which involve a high energy consumption. Energy management systems such as the ISO 50.001 include a complete and comprehensive audit procedure for regular annual energy performance assessments where, as much as 85% of the energy demands must be analysed. The energy efficiency measures selected must be followed up and the saving verified according to suitable energy measurement and verification protocols.

Energy savings are the action drivers in these audits. Nevertheless, little attention, if any, is paid to the assessment and exploitation of energy flexibility in companies. This flexibility implies the shift of energy demands to more convenient periods of time to benefit from lower energy prices, higher self-consumption rates or to be able to respond to a market signal from a system operator for grid congestion management. Flexibility does not necessarily lead to energy savings and may even result in additional energy consumption associated with energy storage losses or process inefficiencies. All flexibility sources require a previous investment, and the utilisation entails a cost that must be calculated and confronted with the expected benefits of the flexibility activation.

Energy flexibility can be classified according to several factors. When looking at the utilisation period timeframe we can make the distinction between long term and short-term flexibility.

- **Long term flexibility.** Referring to flexibility dispatched at a time horizon longer than one day.
- **Short term flexibility.** It is the most usual and refers to flexibility to be used immediately and within a day timeframe.

Talking about the destination of the flexibility, there are two types:

- **Implicit flexibility.** It comes as a result of a conscious decision made by an energy consumer in response to an external market signal (energy price, availability of self-generated energy, etc.). It is rather unpredictable and depends to a great extent on the strength of the signal and the willingness of the consumers to react to that signal.

Usually this flexibility is upwards (energy reduction), implying an energy increase at any point of time later (it is not savings). Moreover, this type of flexibility does not provide direct economic compensation, but it can lead to economic benefits by shifting consumption to more convenient times or utilizing self-generated resources or storage.

- **Explicit flexibility.** This flexibility is triggered in response to a market agreement between a grid operator and a consumer to change the energy pattern at a specific time (event), usually imminent, and for a given duration, usually short. This flexibility can be upwards (temporary energy reduction) or downwards (temporary energy increase). To ensure the correct dispatch of the flexibility these events are usually automatic and controlled by a third party (grid or system operator, flexibility aggregator or market agent). The flexibility provided during the event is estimated through a Measurement and Verification Protocol (PMV) and compensated at the price previously bided.

Industrial processes are really interesting for demand response as they involve large amounts of energy and few decision makers, thus simplifying the process of flexibility elicitation. In addition, energy-intensive processes are usually highly monitored and controlled, facilitating the measurement and management of energy transactions. Flexibility is usually associated with electricity, but strategies can also be deployed on fuel or gas consumers. However, the usual constant gas tariffs and the absence of congestion and management issues on gas grids makes these energy carriers less appealing for flexibility schemes.

In any flexibility audit there is a number of internal and external roles to be played by different professional profiles according to the following definitions:

- **Client company management.** They request for the audit and evaluate the final results and conclusions presented by the auditor lead. They should ensure that the necessary priority and means are assigned to the endeavour, and work to smoothen the way and resolve conflicts in between functional areas of the company.
- **Client company production and maintenance responsible.** They are responsible for providing all necessary data about the product, the process and the equipment involved. This team should include a product and quality expert to illustrate about the quality requirements of the product and the process boundary conditions to comply with the target quality. In the same way, a process and equipment expert should be on board to give advice about the involved equipment and the energy management of the involved equipment.
- **Client company purchase and finance responsible.** This profile is in charge of providing economic data for cost and benefit analysis, as well as commodity and energy supplying costs.
- **Auditor lead.** This role is responsible for defining the objectives and scope with the client company and leads the energy and economic assessment of the flexibility

sources. Auditor is the communication focal point coordinates the auditing team tasks and supervises the final recommendations and presents them to the client company.

- **Auditor technical staff.** This team is a technically skilled team of experts in energy management and audits. They need to provide the necessary knowledge on the involved technologies and the expertise on energy audits. They identify and assess the flexibility sources and check their economic and technical feasibility, ending with the recommendation proposal.
- **Energy retail company.** This role is external to the audit and the involvement is not mandatory but advisable. A reliable retail company can advise about the best dynamic tariffs to maximise the benefits of an implicit flexibility scheme. They can also buy or compensate the energy surplus to the grid at the best possible price. They should be a partner whose market knowledge may be of value for the consumer.
- **Demand response aggregator.** In case of explicit demand response strategies, the representation in the market by a flexibility aggregator to meet the minimum energy bids is inevitable for medium or small companies, and for many large companies as well. This entity will be the link between the company and the market, uniting the grid operators' request of flexibility with the potential flexibility of the company to respond to a grid management issue. The aggregator should sign flexibility contracts with their customers and convey all market signals to them to build up enough interest and flexibility offers to meet the market needs. They would sign up smart contracts for every event for a committed energy upwards or downwards and a retribution price with the interested consumers, and trigger the energy shift automatically or manually. They are in charge of measuring and verifying the delivered flexibility with an appropriate and previously agreed PMV and settle the balance with each participating consumer proportionally to their verified participation after the event. Data transparency and collaboration is required between consumer and aggregator.

The main steps in an energy flexibility audit are the following:

- **Audit objectives and scope.** In this initial phase the specific process stages, products, facilities and energy demands are delimited for the audit. It is important to decide the purpose of the flexibility (implicit, explicit, both). In case the flexibility audit completes an energy audit, it is logical to assume that the scope of the audit will remain the same. In general, the scope of a flexibility audit can be conducted at the plant level or at the process level. In this case, the methodology to be applied at the process level is developed. It is recommended that, once results are obtained for individual processes, the similarities between different processes are analyzed to aggregate them and enable joint participation in flexibility actions.
- **Industrial process characterisation.** This phase is common with the energy audit and requires an exhaustive analysis of the products, processes, energy demands, energy generation, and energy costs involved, as a starting point for the assessment. The direct engagement of the company's technical and production staff is key for

auditors to understand the product quality requirements and the process boundary limits.

- **Flexibility sources characterisation.** This phase goes into the identification of the different existing flexibility sources and potential future sources that can be implemented as recommendations. These sources may be of different nature and usually come from:
 - **Process-driven flexibility:** this flexibility includes the production inherent flexibility to change the production scheduling, the product throughput (or velocity of output) or the company's capacity to put production totally or partially on hold for the duration of an event. This flexibility is driven by economic parameters. Continuous flow processes are usually not suitable for this type of flexibility. Neither are labour-intensive processes. However, this source of flexibility is very common in automatic processes with large buffers in between stages that allow to keep production going while halting some phases for a while.
 - **Energy storage flexibility:** Storing energy at times of low cost or high availability with the capacity to release it as a response to a market-triggered flexibility event or at times of higher energy costs can be a suitable and straightforward source of flexibility. Most common energy storage systems are:
 - Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS), with daily cycles that adapt perfectly to the generation profile of renewable energy generation systems such as photovoltaic (PV), accumulating energy surplus in high solar radiation hours, and releasing it when the sun goes down.
 - Thermal energy storage, in fluids such as water or oil. Energy surplus can be converted into process heat and stored in tanks for later use. The dimension of the tanks is to be designed according to the amount of energy to store, the process heat requirements and the energy surplus.Important parameters are the energy storage capacity, the State of Charge (SoC) and the regeneration and depletion times.
 - **Process Hybrid flexibility:** This source of flexibility is provided by hybrid systems that can use two or more energy carriers to supply the energy demand. Hybridisation is usually supported by electricity and a fuel, either gas, biogas, gasoil or even hydrogen. Hybrid kilns may play with different electricity-based supplies such as electric-arc heating, microwave, induction heating, combined with the combustion of one or more fuels. Relying on the amount of fuels used, the electricity demand in the furnace can be modulated to adapt to different flexibility profiles, upwards or downwards.
At this point, the availability of utilizing RES instead of energy grid is also considered.

- **Characterisation of the different sources of energy flexibility.** Once the flexibility sources are identified and technical feasibility is assessed, the flexibility potential is calculated based on several factors:
 - **Flexible power**, maximum and minimum power to be shifted from every source at a given time, in kW.
 - **Duration** in which the above power can be shifted. Often, it is a combination of both power and duration, that must be assessed to obtain the energy flexibility.
 - **Triggering time.** Point in time when the flexible energy is available. In the case of explicit energy, the triggering time is the event time. For implicit flexibility, the hour ahead is the latest and most accurate estimate of flexibility that can be done.
 - **Latency time.** Interval of time elapsed since the activation of the system flexibility and the actual energy shift. This is almost negligible in electricity demands but often high in thermal processes with high inertia.

An iterative process of validation and adjustment should be followed until all existing and proposed new flexibility sources are fully characterised and understood, testing them in real production environments and fine-tuning the above factors for a correct deployment of any flexibility strategy.

- **Economic feasibility of the flexibility sources.** The decision of flexibility usage and destination should be based on economic parameters. For each event and flexibility source an estimate of costs and benefits should be made to support the energy and process manager's decision whether to trigger the energy shift and the amount of flexibility to use. Benefits must exceed costs for every management decision, and the best strategy is the one that maximizes economic results.
 - **Energy flexibility costs.** These costs include capital costs or equipment usage costs for equipment fully devoted to the provision of the flexibility such as batteries, process and production costs linked to the production plan change, energy losses at storage or transfer, and the energy management costs.
 - **Energy flexibility benefits.** These benefits include economic savings from the internal use of flexibility in relation to Time of Use dynamic tariffs or market indexed prices. In case of external use, the benefits would come from the DR markets.
- **Flexibility audit conclusions and recommendations.** After the technical assessment and economic analysis, the recommendations to exploit or further enhance the flexibility provision of an industrial process are presented to the customer. The lines of action follow three directions:
 - **Immediate flexibility exploitation.** If the technical and economic feasibility assessments show positive results. Triggering criteria and destination targets should be proposed for the selected sources by means of parameter monitoring and threshold setting.

- **Data management for flexibility decision making.** Energy and production historic and real time data is key to ensure accuracy in energy flexibility management. Two aspects must be carefully designed:
 - **Data collection and storage in real time.** Systems to capture and store energy and production monitoring of the key parameters that drive the product and the energy flows must be put in place to assist production managers make the best use of the available flexibility in the process.
 - **Data analysis and intelligence** that enable real time calculations of energy demand and generation forecasts of the default scenario, in order to compare the energy costs with the flexibility usage scenario and optimise the different assets to make the highest benefit of the energy management strategy. This decision support system avoids mistakes and ensures continuous scenario evaluation on a 24-hour ahead basis, with fine refinements made on an hour-ahead basis.
 - **Recommendations for flexibility potential increase.** Judging on the existing flexibility sources and the benefit potential of extending further the flexibility in the process, new investments on flexibility assets can be analysed such as new or large storage systems, in-process buffers, new generation capacity or hybrid energy vector capabilities. For the right assessment of the proposed investments, capital costs, life expectancy and estimated flexibility exploitation results should be estimated to calculate payback times and return on investment metrics to assist company management in making investment decisions. Where possible, the new flexibility assets should be validated in real production environments.
- **Presentation of results and conclusions.** The auditor leader presents the results of the audit and the outstanding recommendations for the immediate use of the available flexibility and for the investments needed to increase the flexibility potential of the process. Once the initial objectives of the audit have been covered and communicated the audit can be closed.

The full flexibility audit procedure is summarised in the following flow chart (figure 9).

This methodology was applied to identify and assess the flexibility of the three ELITHE demonstration thermal processes as they are now and propose measures to increase the flexibility in the innovative processes under design in ELITHE. The results are presented hereafter.

Figure 9. Flexibility audit flow chart.

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3.2 Frits melting flexibility audit

Audit objective and Scope

The objective of this flexibility audit is to determine the flexibility currently available in the frits melting process. The scope is limited to the boundaries of the currently installed kiln and the associated auxiliary processes necessary for frit production at this stage. The auxiliary processes are water quenching, product drying, exhaust gas thermal recovery and oxygen generation. However, only some of these processes will be modified with the new electric smelter: these are exhaust gas thermal recovery and oxygen generation.

Industrial process characterization

The process energy characterization was carried out in the previous chapter, where a schematic detailed the main equipment components, as well as the inputs and outputs of the facility.

Regarding production, the operation runs 24 hours a day, seven days a week, indicating a continuous production process. The reference smelter chosen has a nominal capacity of 2 tons and a productivity of 1 t/h, implying 24 t/day and 7,920 t/year of frit production. The average melting time for the material inside the furnace is 120 minutes. These parameters are crucial to maintaining the desired quality and efficiency in the frit production process. In terms of downtime, there is an annual maintenance shutdown that lasts for over one month.

The variables affecting energy consumption are related to the condition of the raw materials, which must not contain more than 0.5% moisture. Additionally, frit recipe changes involve emptying the kilns and restarting them. On average, there are 3 recipe changes per month, which amounts to a 33 changes per year over 11 months of operation.

Considering that this is a process involving the mixing of raw materials to produce a glass composed of various inorganic oxides, the quality of the frit can be negatively affected by numerous parameters: Fuel flow, Temperature, Excess of air, Kiln pressure, Speed of screw feeder.

The mixture of inorganic oxides used as raw material has a particle size distribution ranging between 200 and 500 microns. The process requires the furnace to operate at a minimum temperature of 1540 °C and a maximum temperature of 1560 °C. This short range leaves very little margin, if any, to energy flexibility in terms of thermal storage.

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However, throughput variations offer a more promising source of flexibility: the feeding system utilized is a screw feeder, with a feeding velocity ranging between 0.8 and 1.2 t/h which is a 40% range variation from 1550 rpm to 2450 rpm of the screw feeder. This flexibility is heavily subject to keeping the thermal properties and homogeneity of the material inside the furnace, limiting energy variations to a maximum 50 rpm/h acceleration or deceleration, which entails 2.5% energy variation rate per hour or 57.1 kWh per ton and per hour. The total maximum flexibility (40%) would represent up to 914 kWh/t to be achieved in about 18 hours of steady constant speed variation. In nominal conditions, when operating at 1 t/h throughput, the maximum flexibility upwards or downwards would amount up to +-457 kWh/t in 9 hours at a constant rate of 57.1 kWh/t per hour.

For short-term energy flexibility, we can consider that 1% flexibility achieved via feeder speed variations would mean 22.85 kWh/t in 24 minutes or 57.1 kWh/t in one hour. The energy change is not immediate but is gradually achieved, which limits the applicability of this potential energy flexibility source. The screw feeder speed is regulated by the amount of material in the furnace which, in turn, is driven by the extraction rate. Low extraction rates slow down the speed at which material is being fed into the smelter.

The production process utilizes two primary energy resources: electricity and natural gas. Nevertheless, the present kilns run fully on gas combustion, usually supported with oxi-combustion. The oxygen production is also procured inhouse. The share of oxi-combustion has no effect on electricity consumption and would not be converted into an electricity flexibility knob. Even in terms of thermal energy demand, burners are not flexible and do not admit oxi-combustion and conventional combustion simultaneously. The oxygen rate in the comburent mix cannot be considered a source of energy demand flexibility.

Electricity is procured through a contract where approximately 60% of the price is fixed and 40% is indexed to market fluctuations. The energy term or the non-regulated cost of energy is market-driven and depends on the fluctuations of the wholesale market in the 24 h ahead spot market and the system balancing costs. Hence, there is a possibility to use these variable tariffs to run an implicit internal flexibility demand program to shift consumptions from high-cost hours to cheaper hours, and benefit from the energy hourly cost differences. Natural gas is purchased with 100% indexed pricing to a local company. All in all, gas prices do not allow for any implicit flexibility strategy as there are no time-of-use signals.

Flexibility sources characterisation

Process-driven flexibility:

From the perspective of product quality assurance, the following operational points are observed, which can contribute to some degree of flexibility.

Table 5: Frit melting process-driven maximum energy flexibility in kWh/t

	Value	Unit	Flexible Energy [kWh/t]
Change of temperature for the reference frit	+10°	°C	+30
Change of feeding velocity in Screw feeder	+0.2	t/h	+457

Another important point to study process-driven flexibility is the available level of control. The control system of the process employs an automatic approach utilizing PID and SCADA systems. This system manages a range of control variables including temperatures, feeding speeds and combustion parameters.

The control strategy focuses on specific variables to manage the process effectively. For instance, the inner temperature of the furnace, set at 1,550 °C, directly controls the gas flow rate of the main burner. This automatic adjustment of the burner gas flow ensures that the desired temperature is maintained, enhancing the efficiency of the process. Additionally, the height of the raw materials inside the furnace is monitored to determine the melting rate. If the height is high, the screw feeder slows down, and if the height is low, the screw feeder speeds up. This dynamic adjustment helps optimize the melting process, which is ultimately driven by the extraction rate of the molten frits.

By precisely controlling these variables, the system introduces a significant degree of flexibility in managing the energy consumption of the process. Maintaining optimal temperatures and adjusting the raw material feed rate based on real-time measurements allows for efficient energy use, reducing waste and improving overall process efficiency. This adaptability not only conserves energy but also enhances the reliability and consistency of the production process.

The use of recycled frits as raw material offers energy flexibility due to the savings in melting energy as the content of recycled frits increases in the feeding mix. There are two types of recycled frits: Filter dust and recycled frits from product recipe changes. The variation in demand due to the use of recycled frit may be an option but depends on the availability of this material, the only source of which is internal. The use of recycled frit dust might supply 1.6% of energy reduction per 10% extra recycled frits in the raw material composition of some frit recipes, but the effect of any mix change is not immediate and would take some time to materialize in an energy decrease. The use of this source of flexibility downwards is not economically feasible as it results in an energy increase.

Energy storage flexibility:

Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS): no inventory is recorded in the current situation. Implementing an electrical energy storage system in the process can significantly enhance the process's electricity flexibility. The energy storage system allows for the capture and storage of electricity during periods of low demand or when renewable energy sources are abundant and cost-effective. This stored energy can then be utilized during peak demand periods or when the cost of electricity is higher, reducing the dependency on the grid and stabilizing energy costs and permitting to the company to integrate implicit flexibility strategies. The advantages of such a system include improved energy efficiency, reduced operational costs, and enhanced sustainability through better integration of renewable energy sources. However, the system also has some disadvantages, such as the high initial capital investment required for installation, potential maintenance costs, and the need for precise management to avoid energy losses or inefficiencies. Additionally, the storage capacity must be carefully matched to the energy demands of the frit production process to ensure optimal performance.

Thermal energy storage (TES): No inventory is recorded in the current situation. At this point it is needed to specify that a thermal energy storage system could, in theory, provide independence from the natural gas supply by storing heat generated from electricity, thereby offering a backup during grid outages. However, in processes like frit production, where extremely high temperatures are required, current thermal storage technologies are neither efficient nor capable of storing the necessary amount of heat at a reasonable cost. The required storage capacity to maintain such high temperatures would demand substantial investment, both in terms of materials and infrastructure, making it economically unfeasible. As a result, true supply independence is more effectively achieved through the incorporation of an alternative thermal energy generation mechanisms, such as onsite cogeneration systems or the use of alternative fuels or a hybrid furnace, how is proposed as solution in this project and will be explained in chapter 5. These systems can provide the necessary thermal energy continuously and reliably, without the limitations posed by existing thermal storage technologies, thus ensuring the process's resilience and operational continuity.

Process Hybrid flexibility:

The process at present involves energy consumption with the following distribution: 99.3% natural gas and 0.7 % electricity. As mentioned earlier, the furnaces are equipped with natural gas burners and, in the current situation, do not have any alternative feed systems that would allow switching the source from which the thermal energy required to carry out the frit melting and firing process is obtained.

Although an exhaust gas thermal recovery system is already available, it is of no use for energy flexibility in a fully electric process.

Also, an automatic connection to an ancillary energy generation system to guarantee the supply in case of failure of the general energy system is available.

On the other hand, the auxiliary processes use electrical energy; in this case, the electrical energy is sourced both from the power grid and from a 947 kWp photovoltaic installation that produces 430 MWh/year, which is 100 % self-consumed. Electrifying the process would soar electricity consumption, allowing for a much more powerful generation facility.

The combination of a greater PV generation asset enabling some energy surplus, with Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) that would store those energy surplus would be a very valuable flexibility source. This storage should be done on daily cycles, storing at generation peak times and releasing the energy at times of no generation and high energy prices. It could also be used to participate in explicit demand response schemes for grid management services to grid operators.

Process hybrid flexibility entails indeed the flexible combination of several distinct energy carriers that can totally or partially replace the electricity consumption to achieve a certain degree of flexibility in the electricity demand. This is currently not possible as the kilns are fully running on gas. However, the new eLITHE equipment is a hybrid system that intends to integrate gas burners and electricity arc heaters. The default system is originally conceived to use gas just to start up the process until the materials are fully molten and the system reached the steady continuous stage. At that point, only electricity would be used. However, it is worth investigating to what extent the two heating systems can be used simultaneously to replace a variable amount of electricity consumption by gas-generated heat and thus, shift electricity consumption at a given time or event. This will be analysed in more detail in chapter 5.

Recommendations and conclusions

Having followed the flexibility audit methodology in TCID, the following main considerations can be highlighted:

- The greatest source of flexibility is the feed rate of the raw material, which allows a variation in fusion energy proportional to the speed variation, ranging from 0.8 t/h to 1.2 t/h. This is +- 20% energy flexibility but on hourly basis it is limited to +-2.5% due to the low variation rate of the screw feeder to avoid a too rapid cooling or heating inside the furnace. The feeding rate is driven by the extraction rate.
- Flexibility due to thermal storage is negligible with a melting temperature variation of +-10°.
- The variation in demand due to the use of recycled frit may be an option but depends on the availability of this material, the only source of which is internal. The use of recycled frit dust might supply 1.6% of energy reduction per 10% extra recycled frits in the raw material composition of some frit recipes, but the effect of any mix change is not immediate and would take some time to materialize in an energy decrease. The use of this source of flexibility downwards is not economically feasible as it results in an energy increase.

- Green hydrogen production is a good source of flexibility but only feasible in the event of high renewable production surplus or periods of very low energy prices. H₂ can be injected combined with gas for direct combustion or for electricity generation with an H₂ cell. In the current scenario, there is no generation surplus or zero electricity price periods.
- Oxy-combustion does not seem to be a source of flexibility in an electricity-driven process. Even if electric heating is supported by additional gas burning, oxy-combustion would contribute to the process flexibility in a very limited extent.
- The current self-consumption level does not provide flexibility because there are no energy surplus. There could be more if RES generation capacity were increased, in face of an electrification scenario.
- The use of electrical heating probably needs the support of gas burners for the process startup until the material in the kiln gets molten and the process attains stationary condition. The hybrid use of dual sources, electricity and gas, would allow some flexibility in the new 200 kg/h oven. This is the most versatile and promising source of future flexibility, but testing should be carried out first to assess limitations and boundaries.

3.3 Brick firing flexibility audit

Audit objective and Scope

The objective of this flexibility audit is to determine the current energy flexibility available in the perforated brick firing and drying processes. The scope is limited to the boundaries of the currently installed tunnel kiln and the associated auxiliary processes necessary for brick production at this stage. The auxiliary processes are air blowers, air extraction and a car movement system used to transport bricks along the tunnel.

Industrial process characterization

The process energy characterization was carried out in the previous chapter, where a schematic detailed the main stages of the process, the equipment components, and the inputs and outputs of the facility.

The brick manufacturing process operates continuously, with production running 24 hours a day, yielding a total of 300 tons per day. Scheduled maintenance stops occur but account for no more than 10 % of the total time throughout the year. This means that 90 % of the time, bricks are being produced continuously, resulting in an annual production of 120,888 tons. The average firing time for the material inside the furnace is 24-26 hours.

The raw materials used in the firing process include clay, sawdust, and residues from the paper industry, with a flow rate ranging from 4.14 kg/s to higher levels. The process operates at a temperature range with a minimum of approximately 100 °C when the dried bricks are fed into the tunnel kiln, and a maximum of 1000 °C during firing. The firing process requires

a minimum time of 24 to 26 hours, depending on the specific material properties and kiln conditions. This narrow time range and high-temperature requirement offer limited flexibility for energy adjustments within the firing process. Variations in throughput could potentially provide some level of flexibility, but this is constrained by the need to maintain the thermal properties and uniformity of the bricks inside the kiln. The precise control of material flow and kiln temperature is crucial, as any deviation could affect the final product quality, limiting the potential for significant energy flexibility during the firing phase.

In brick production, two primary energy sources are utilized: natural gas and electricity. The firing section of the tunnel kiln primarily uses natural gas, as well as the drying section. During the firing process, natural gas is combusted to generate the heat required for baking the bricks, while electricity powers the movement of the kiln cars and the air flow fans. In the drying process, electricity is used to operate the kiln car movement, air blowers, and air extraction systems.

In the brick manufacturing process, drying and thermal energy recovery are critical components associated with the firing stage. The drying process reduces the moisture content in the greenware from 25% to 2% before entering the firing kiln. This drying phase consumes approximately 14,872 MWh/yr of natural gas annually, equating to 0.1 kWh per kilogram of material.

The variables affecting energy consumption are related to the maximum temperature reached inside the tunnel kiln. In the brick firing process, the maximum value of this parameter is 1,000 °C, while in drying process temperature should not exceed 100 °C. Additionally, production rate affects thermal energy consumption significantly, the average value being around 15 t/h. Also, temperatures should not exceed the locational set values to avoid damage due to formation of cracks.

Flexibility sources characterisation

Process-driven flexibility

The brick production process is primarily governed by a temperature-regulated control system that ensures consistent product quality by managing key variables such as car speed, air flow rates, and temperature at various axial locations within the tunnel kiln. The process operates at full kiln capacity, utilizing 100% of its power capability. To maintain the required temperature profiles, adjustments can be made to the flow rates of air inlets and outlets, as well as the fuel input. This inherent control strategy offers some degree of energy flexibility, particularly through the modulation of air flow rates and fuel supply.

However, given the high energy demands of the kiln operating at full capacity, the scope for downward energy flexibility is limited. Reducing energy input would likely impact the temperature regulation, thus affecting the overall quality and uniformity of the bricks produced.

Consequently, while the process can adapt to variations in energy input, the potential for significant energy flexibility is constrained by the need to maintain strict temperature control and full operational capacity.

Energy storage flexibility

Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS): no inventory is recorded in the current situation.

Thermal energy storage (TES): No inventory is recorded in the current situation.

Process Hybrid flexibility

To enhance the flexibility of the brick production process through hybridization, strategic integration of renewable energy sources and optimization of waste heat recovery are essential.

The thermal energy recovery system employs a regenerative afterburner to treat flue gases from the tunnel kiln. These flue gases exit the kiln at 147 °C and are then heated to 468 °C in the afterburner before being directed to a heat exchanger. The heat exchanger transfers this energy to the dryer, providing a part the necessary energy for drying the green bricks before they enter the tunnel kiln at 182 °C. This process effectively recycles waste heat, significantly enhancing energy efficiency. However, the energy savings achieved through this recovery system offer limited flexibility; using it for downward flexibility (reducing energy use) would negate the energy savings, making it impractical.

To further hybridize the process, solar thermal systems could be introduced to preheat the air used in the drying phase, which would reduce reliance on fossil fuels. However, it's important to note that the temperature provided by solar thermal systems typically does not exceed 70°C. Additionally, implementing biomass boilers could supplement the existing natural gas system, offering a renewable heat source that can be integrated with minimal disruption to the current setup.

A 634 kWp photovoltaic system is already in place, providing a portion of the electricity required. The estimate of annual generation is around 950 MWh/yr. About 60 % of this amount is self-consumed (570 MWh/yr) but not in the thermal firing process. This is about a 24 % of the total electricity consumption of the brick manufacturing plant. Hence it is clear that there is room to invest in self-consumption facilities to increase self-dependency and feed the newly designed electricity-powered process.

Recommendations

Extend the current RES generation capacity to increase the coverage of self-consumed energy and allow for an electrification of the firing process.

Co-funded by
the European Union.

Install BESS to gain a clear flexibility asset, supported by larger RES generation capacity.

Explore the electric flexibility of the new electricity driven kilns, seeking a hybrid solution that combines both green hydrogen and electricity in the thermal process.

3.4 Alumina calciner flexibility audit

Audit objective and Scope

The objective of this flexibility audit is to determine the current energy flexibility available in the alumina calciner process. The scope is limited to the boundaries of the currently installed vertical calciners and the associated auxiliary processes necessary for high-purity alumina production at this stage.

Industrial process characterization

The process energy characterization was carried out in the previous chapter, where a schematic detailed the main equipment components for both types of calciner studied Circulating fluid-bed reactor furnace and gas suspension vertical calciner, as well as the main inputs and outputs of the facility.

Regarding production, the operation is conducted on a continuous schedule, running 8,000 hours per year, reflecting a high-intensity production process. The system undergoes planned stoppages amounting to 760 hours annually, which encompass maintenance and other operational halts critical for maintaining equipment reliability and process stability. The facility achieves an annual production output of 639,377 tons, with a production rate of 79.92 tons per hour. These operational parameters are optimized to sustain the desired throughput and ensure consistent quality of the alumina. Effective downtime management and precise scheduling of maintenance activities are vital to minimize interruptions and uphold the efficiency of the production process.

The main variables influencing energy consumption in the calcination process are the condition of the raw materials, particularly particle size and the percentage of raw material rejection. Fine particle sizes enhance thermal efficiency due to increased surface area, enabling faster heat transfer and reducing energy requirements; however, excessively fine particles may cause agglomeration and operational inefficiencies, potentially increasing energy consumption. Larger particles, on the other hand, require prolonged heating, thereby increasing energy demands. A high raw material rejection rate signifies that a substantial portion of the energy input is expended on non-utilizable material, resulting in higher specific energy consumption per ton of alumina produced. Therefore, precise control of particle size and minimizing raw material rejection are critical to optimizing energy efficiency in the calcination process.

The primary raw material utilized is Gibbsite ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$), containing a moisture below 8 % more typically around 4 % entry into the smelter. The feed rate of the raw material is maintained at a consistent flow of 132 tons per hour of trihydrate alumina, resulting in the production of 80 tons per hour of SGA. This flow rate is constant and cannot be altered, emphasizing the importance of understanding energy consumption strictly within the operational constraints of the calciner. The stable feed rate ensures that energy consumption is directly tied to the inherent properties of the Gibbsite and its interaction with the calcination process, rather than any variability in the input flow.

The production process relies on two main energy resources: electricity and natural gas. Electricity consumption is measured at 0.101 MJ/kg and is primarily used to power mechanical components, feeders, and pressurized air systems, which are critical for maintaining operational stability and efficiency. Natural gas is the heat energy source, consumed at a rate of 2.97 MJ/kg, supplying the thermal energy necessary for the calcination process. The specific energy consumption in continuous flow is 3.07 GJ per ton, indicating the combined impact of both energy inputs on the overall energy efficiency of the production system.

Energy storage flexibility

Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS): no inventory is recorded in the current situation.

Thermal energy storage (TES): No inventory is recorded in the current situation.

Process Hybrid flexibility

The innovative calcination equipment based on microwave technology will not require dual energy source usage. Hence, this potential flexibility source is not considered in the present approach.

Currently, the process employs residual heat recovery for preheating raw materials, the flue gases, with an inlet temperature of 135-140 °C and a flow rate of 39 m³/sec, are effectively used to transfer heat to the raw material preheating stage, enhancing the overall energy efficiency of the calciner. The absence of flue gases in the electrical process will make subsequent operation of the heat recovery system unnecessary. Additionally, while the company facilities include a Combined Heat and Power (CHP) unit, it is currently not employed in the calcination process,

Recommendations

Increase RES generation capacity to extend the coverage of self-consumed energy and allow for an electrification of the calcination process.

Install BESS to gain a clear flexibility asset, supported by larger RES generation capacity.

4 Energy prices and remuneration forecast

In this chapter, UNIGE preliminarily investigated the potential economic viability of the electrification of the project Demo site processes, particularly starting from the self-consumption of local PV production and considering an increase of the PV capacity towards the potential full coverage of the local heating demand also thanks to the integration of energy storages, both batteries and thermal energy storages.

For this purpose (considering their more limited size and operating temperatures, as well as the presence of an existing PV system) TCID and brjcm +s were investigated in more detail.

4.1 Assessment of METLEN-TCID-brick firing processes opportunities for electrification

An initial analysis was carried out to assess whether the electrification of the ceramic industry (with the TCID and brjcm +s as the primary focus of Chapter 4, and the METLEN demosite from the aluminium sector partially investigated due to its scale) could lead to economic as well as environmental advantages, and what changes in the energy market would be necessary to achieve this.

This evaluation was based on the assumption of complete electrification of the process, with the required electric energy being purchased from the grid to cover the thermal energy demand of each plant, minus any on-site self-production. The comparison between electrification and the current gas-based solution is based on the Levelized Cost Of Heating (LCOH), defined according to Eq. (1) as the sum of all costs (CAPEX C_C , OPEX C_O = maintenance costs C_M , fuel costs C_F , energy costs C_{el}) during lifetime, minus the revenues R , divided by the overall energy production E . The lifetime of the plant LT is assumed to be equal to 20 years.

$$LCOH = \frac{\sum_{LT}(C_C + C_O - R)}{\sum_{LT} E} = \frac{\sum_{LT}(C_C + C_M + C_F + C_{el} - R)}{\sum_{LT} E} \quad (1)$$

4.1.1 METLEN

The Greek energy market is characterized by an average natural gas (NG) price of 48.9 €/MWh [2], an average electricity cost of 154.6 €/MWh [1] and a carbon tax of 26.69 €/tCO₂ [3]. Under these conditions, electrification of the Metlen process would be more costly, being characterized by a LCOH of 162.73 €/MWh_{th}, against the current natural gas one of 59.725 €/MWh_{th}. A quick analysis highlighted that the same LCOH could be obtained under any of the three following changes:

- The cost of NG increased to 141.61 €/MWh (a cost reached during the 2022 NG crisis).
- The cost of electric energy decreased to 56.74 €/MWh (close to Greek PV LCOE).
- The carbon tax increased to 536.65 €/tCO₂ (if keeping NG costs as the baseline – a value that is far to be achieved even in long period projections).

It is evident that all these conditions are quite far from the current scenario, and therefore alternative solutions must be researched to improve the techno-economic feasibility of electrification. Since energy demand of Metlen is very high, full electricity self-production does not seem feasible due to the huge size of the PV plant needed. Therefore, economic feasibility of its electrification will strongly depend on the evolution of the energy market and on decarbonization policies but could be aided by the implementation of hybrid solutions and the integration of energy storage.

4.1.2 TCID

The Spanish energy market is characterized by an average natural gas (NG) cost of 54.70 €/MWh [2], an average electricity cost of 87.11€/MWh [1] and a carbon tax of 15.00€/tCO₂ [3]. Under these conditions and already considering the existing PV production exploitation, electrification of the TCID process would be more costly, being characterized by a LCOH of 91.69 €/MWh_{th}, against the current one of 63.80 €/MWh_{th}. A quick analysis highlighted that the same LCOH could be obtained under any of the three following changes:

- The cost of NG increased to 77.67 €/MWh.
- The cost of electric energy decreased to 60.61 €/MWh (a value even higher than Spanish PV LCOE)
- The carbon tax increased to 185€/tCO₂. (if keeping NG costs as the baseline – a value that is double than in long period projections)

In this case, due to the lower cost of electricity in the country, these conditions are closer to the current scenario, particularly considering PV self-exploitation as a potential alternative solution to improve the techno-economic feasibility of electrification.

Considering the present energy market, an investigation on the optimal size of photovoltaic (PV) panels to be installed was performed. The goal is to understand if the same LCOH of the gas-based process can be reached by exploiting self-production of electric energy.

Figure 10 shows how the LCOH of electrified heating (EH) is affected by the size of the PV plant. It is possible to observe that the LCOH_{EH} shows moderate variations between 2 and 5.5 MW of nominal power, with a minimum reached for a size of PV equal to about x1.25 of the hourly thermal demand of the process. At this value, the exploitation of self-generated power is optimal, reducing the amount of energy to be purchased from the grid, and thus lowering costs. However, excessively oversizing the PV is detrimental for the LCOH, because capital costs increase and the PV production exceeds the demand of plant (the

revenues from selling the energy to grid are lower than the savings derived from self-production).

Figure 10. Cost of heating for an electrified process (TCID) while varying the PV size.

4.1.3 IZF

The German energy market is characterized by an average natural gas (NG) cost of 62.20 €/MWh [2], an average electricity cost of 95.04€/MWh [1] and a carbon tax of 45.00€/tCO₂ [3]. Despite a much higher carbon tax than in Spain, also the electrification of the IZF process would not be economically viable, being characterized (even already considering the existing PV production exploitation) by a LCOH of 100.04 €/MWh_{th}, against the current one of 78.2 €/MWh_{th}. A quick analysis highlighted that the same LCOH of the gas-based process could be obtained under any of the three following changes:

- The cost of NG increased to 85.19 €/MWh.
- The cost of electric energy decreased to 74.30 €/MWh (a value not distant from German PV LCOE)
- The carbon tax increased to 118.20 €/tCO₂. (if keeping NG costs as the baseline – a value not distant from long period projections' ones)

These conditions are farther from the current scenario than in the Spanish one, but shows that PV self-consumption could improve the techno-economic feasibility of electrification. Similarly to TCID, an investigation on the optimal size of photovoltaic (PV) panels to be installed was performed while considering the current energy market. The goal is to understand if the same LCOH of the gas-based process can be reached by exploiting self-production of electric energy.

Figure 10 shows how the LCOH of electrified heating (EH) is affected by the size of the PV plant. It is possible to observe that the $LCOH_{EH}$ has moderate variations between 0.5 and 4.0 MW of nominal power, with a minimum reached for a size of PV equal to the hourly thermal demand of the process. For this value, the exploitation of self-generated power is optimal, reducing the amount of energy to be purchased from the grid and therefore the costs. However, excessively oversizing the PV is detrimental to the LCOH, as capital costs increase and PV production exceeds plant demand (the revenues from selling energy to the grid are lower than the savings from self-production).

Figure 11. Cost of heating for an electrified process (IZF) while varying the PV size.

4.2 Assessment of TCID-IZF opportunities for electrification with local PV Production and potential energy storage

Following the preliminary results presented in §4.1, which showed the potential viability of using local PV production to drive the electrification of TCID-IZF processes, UNIGE developed a time-dependent methodology that, starting from local irradiation profile, has been able to:

- Evaluate the LCOH of a potential electrification of the processes starting from the existing PV plants (thus heavily relying on the purchase of electricity from the local grids at costs that, as shown, are not sustainable).
- Determine the size of the PV and Energy Storage (TES or Battery) systems needed to maximise the self-consumption of locally produced renewable energy and provide a viable LCOH.

4.2.1 Methodology of Calculation

Two different calculation algorithms were created to analyse via a time-dependent analysis the techno-economic performance of electrification solutions based on the integration of the process with PV+battery and PV+TES. In both cases, the following assumptions (similar to those used to evaluate LCOH in §4.1) were adopted:

- Minimum load of electric heater (EH) = 20%
- EH efficiency = 0.95
- EH nominal load = hourly thermal demand / EH efficiency
- Hourly thermal energy loss in the TES = 0.5%

As the project progresses and more information on the innovative EH technologies is obtained, the EH features (efficiency and minimum load) will be updated accordingly.

According to the information provided by TCID and IZF, the hourly thermal energy demand of both plants was considered as constant, except for 1 month of maintenance when production is stopped. The following data were used in the analysis:

TCID

Hourly Thermal power demand $P_{th} = 2.106 \text{ MW}_{th}$

Peak power capacity of the currently installed PV plant = 0.976 MW_p

IZF

Hourly Thermal power demand $P_{th} = 2.111 \text{ MW}_{th}$

Nominal power output of pre-existing PV = 0.654 MW_p

The same energy market conditions described for Spain and Germany were considered (Sections 4.1.2 and 4.1.3, respectively). For both case studies, the revenues from selling energy surplus from the PV Plant (that cannot be stored in the analysed storage systems) to the national grid are assumed to be equal to 40 €/MWh (a quite favourable value).

Regarding the power generation of the PV, local historical weather data was retrieved for each demo site. Measurements of global horizontal irradiance (GHI) were obtained from the web tool Photovoltaic Geographic Information System (PVGIS), developed by the Joint Research Center (JRC) of the European Commission [4]. For each month, a typical week was defined, and the hourly irradiance was used to compute the electrical energy generated by the PV each hour considering the area of panels A_{PV} and their efficiency η_{PV} (here assumed equal to 20%), according to Eq. (2).

$$E_{PV} = GHI A_{PV} \eta_{PV} \quad (2)$$

Based on these assumptions, the hourly operation of each plant is determined by different algorithms, depending on whether the industrial process is integrated with PV+BESS (Battery Energy Storage System) or PV+TES, with different sizes of the EHs in the two scenarios. Referring to a typical week for each month, a weekly profile of thermal generation is created for each month of the year. From these profiles, monthly and yearly profiles are obtained.

The two algorithms are here described:

PV+EH+BESS

- 1 The renewable energy source (RES) generation from the PV is computed based on the GHI data of the corresponding hour and day.

- 2
 - a) If the RES production is below the minimum EH load, all the energy is stored in the battery. If the battery is full, the excess energy can be sold to the grid.
 - b) If the RES production is over the plant demand, the excess energy is stored in the battery. If the battery is full, the excess energy can be sold to the grid.
 - c) If the RES production is over the minimum EH load and equal or under the plant demand, the RES production is used in the EH to provide thermal energy to the process.

- 3 If part of the thermal demand is not covered by the RES, the missing electrical energy is provided by the battery if available and purchased from the grid otherwise.

Figure 12 shows the logic implemented in the calculation algorithm to evaluate the operation of an electrified process integrated with PV and battery.

Figure 12. Logics implemented in the calculation algorithm to evaluate the operation of an electrified process integrated with PV and battery.

PV+higher scale EH+TES

- 1 The renewable energy source (RES) generation from the PV is computed based on the GHI data of the corresponding hour and day.
- 2
 - a) If the RES production is below the minimum EH load, the missing electrical energy is purchased from the grid to reach the minimum EH load.
 - b) If the RES production exceeds the plant demand, the excess energy is converted into thermal energy by the EH and stored in the TES. If the TES is full, the excess electrical energy can be sold to the grid.
 - c) If the RES production is over the minimum EH load and equal or under the plant demand, the RES production is used in the EH to provide thermal energy to the process.
- 3 If part of the thermal demand is not covered by the RES, the missing thermal energy is provided by the TES if available. Otherwise, electrical energy is purchased from the grid and converted into thermal energy by the EH.

Figure 13 shows the logic implemented in the calculation algorithm to regulate the operation of an electrified process integrated with PV and TES.

where P_{PV} is the nominal power of PV, and the subscripts tot and pre refer to the total and pre-existing PV.

- Cost of battery (purchase and installation) C_{bat} :

$$C_{bat}[k\text{€}] = 200 [k\text{€}/MWh] \cdot E_{bat,nom} [MWh] \quad (5)$$

where $E_{bat,nom}$ is the capacity of the battery.

- Cost of TES (purchase and installation) C_{TES} :

$$C_{TES}[k\text{€}] = 60 [k\text{€}/MWh] \cdot E_{TES,nom} [MWh] \quad (6)$$

where $E_{TES,nom}$ is the capacity of the TES

- Costs of other civil works, considering the need for medium-high power supply to the EH: $C_{works} = 40\%$ of C_{EH} .
- Maintenance costs $C_M [k\text{€}] = 2\%$ of C_C (capital costs, i.e., CAPEX)

$$C_M[k\text{€}] = 2\% C_C \quad (7)$$

4.2.3 Analysed KPIs

The techno-economic analysis was then performed based on the following equations:

- Potential equivalent operating hours (EOH) of the EH powered by the PV in a year:

$$EOH_{EH-PV} = \frac{E_{PV} [MWh]}{P_{EH,nom} [MW]} \quad (8)$$

where $P_{EH,nom}$ is the nominal power of the EH.

- Overall cost of the electric energy purchased by the grid C_{el} :

$$C_{el}[\text{€}] = c_{el,grid} [\text{€}/MWh] \cdot E_{el,grid} [MWh] \quad (9)$$

$$E_{el,grid} [MWh] = E_{th} [MWh] / \eta_{EH} \quad (10)$$

where $E_{el,grid}$ is the energy purchased from the grid and $C_{el,grid}$ is its cost per MWh. Hourly values of $E_{el,grid}$ are obtained by dividing the hourly thermal energy demand by the EH efficiency η_{EH} , which is assumed to be equal to 0.95.

- Overall cost of the natural gas (fuel) C_F :

$$C_F[\text{€}] = c_F [\text{€/MWh}] \cdot E_F[\text{MWh}] \quad (11)$$

$$E_F[\text{MWh}] = E_{th}[\text{MWh}]/\eta_{EH} \quad (12)$$

where E_F is the chemical energy of the natural gas necessary to cover the thermal demand and c_F is the gas cost per MWh. Hourly values of E_F are obtained by dividing the hourly thermal energy demand by the gas burner efficiency η_{EH} , which is assumed to be equal to 0.90.

- Overall capital cost C_c :

$$C_c[\text{k€}] = C_{EH} + C_{bat} + C_{TES} + C_{works} \quad (13)$$

- Maintenance and operation costs (OPEX) $C_O = C_M + C_{el} + C_F$

$$C_O[\text{k€}] = C_M + C_{el} + C_F \quad (3)$$

- Revenues R , obtained from the sale of excess RES production $E_{PV,exc}$ to the grid

$$R[\text{k€}] = c_{el,sold} [\text{€/MWh}] \cdot E_{PV,exc}[\text{MWh}] \quad (4)$$

where $C_{el,sold}$ is the electric energy price when sold to the grid.

These equations are finally used to compute the LCOH according to Eq. (1), referring to only one year of operation.

The economic performance of each technological solution for the electrification of the TCID and IZF demo sites is also evaluated by calculating the payback period (PBP). PBP represents the number of years that are required before the revenues of an investment cover its capital expenses, and in this case it is computed as:

$$PBP[\text{years}] = C_c[\text{k€}] / (E_{th}[\text{MWh}] \cdot (LCOH_{EH} - LCOH_{NG}) [\text{k€/MWh}]) \quad (5)$$

4.3 Storage (TES/BATTERY) Sizing and comparisons in TCID-brick firing processes

In this section, the calculation approach presented in Chapter 4.2.1 is applied to the TCID and brick firing process for the two aforementioned reference scenarios: i) the PV+EH+BESS, ii) the PV+EH+TES.

The goal of this analysis is to determine whether there is an opportunity to optimally size the PV, the EH and the storage (TES or BEES) in order to achieve a parity between the LCOH of the electrified scenario (LCOH_{EH}) and of the current natural gas driven scenario (LCOH_{NG}).

PV plant capacity and BESS size has been therefore varied as multiple of the reference value, that is the “EH power capacity” which has been sized to cover the hourly thermal demand of the process.

Similarly, the PV plant capacity and TES size have been varied as multiples of the reference value, that in this case has been evaluated as the “electric equivalent” of the hourly thermal demand of the process: EH and PV have indeed to have a similar power capacity in order to enable to store excess of energy via thermal media.

The following KPIs have been analyzed: the LCOH and the overall amount of PV production not exploited along the year (Overall RES Wasted).

4.3.1 TCID Demo site

As mentioned above, the possibility to electrify the TCID process thanks to the exploitation of an increased scale PV plant and the integration of storage (BESS and TES) has been evaluated.

Increasing the PV size, the LCOH seems to decrease, but (at the same time) increasing the battery size (in order to maximize PV self-exploitation – Tab.12) brings to a CAPEX increase and a subsequent increase of the LCOH (Tab.8). The values show that regardless of the PV and BESS sizing, the LCOH_{EH} cannot reach parity with LCOH_{NG} (0.064 €/kWh_{th}).

A similar scenario occurs if considering to integrate a TES (instead of a BESS) and overscale the EH to couple it with the scale of the PV plant: despite indeed the TES has a lower CAPEX than the BESS, the increase in EH CAPEX and the need to operate it with electricity purchased from the grid make the two scenarios more or less equivalent both from the LCOH (Tab.9) and from the RES exploitation (Tab.12) point of view.

At this purpose, the possibility to further reduce the CAPEX of the TES (e.g. using ceramic production process wastes as thermal storage media) has been investigated: TES CAPEX

cost function has been varied from 60 €/MWh up to 20 €/MWh. Nevertheless, no significant modifications were appreciated. (Tab.10)

In order to limit the CAPEX of the “TES Scenario”, it was proposed to “decouple” the sizing of the EH and the PV, with the PV Capacity set to 1.5 times the size of the Electric Heater: then the sensitivity analysis on PV/EH and TES scale have been performed. This “decoupling” has a positive impact on “LCOH EH” but may negatively affect the self-exploitation of RES and it never guarantees the parity with the baseline “LCOH NG”. (Tab. 11).

The only way to guarantee a viable LCOH in the electrification scenario, is to oversize the PV plant and enable the sale of excess RES that cannot be fully self-exploited: in this case, particularly for the BESS scenario, the LCOH can become comparable to the baseline NG scenario. (Tab.13)

At the conclusion of the analysis, after reviewing various sensitivity analyses and searching for a compromise between the different KPIs analyzed in the Tables presented here below, the current sizing layouts were considered as the most favorable:

- PV-BESS: PV x2 – BESS x4
- PV-EH-TES: PV x1.5 – EH x1 – TES x3

And such sizing will be analyzed in the next paragraphs in the variation of the energy context parameters.

Table 6: TCID scenario – PV+EH+BES sizing sensitivity analysis and LCOH variation

	LCOH Torrecid (LCOH NG: 0,06078 without Carbon Tax - with Carbon Tax: 0,064)														
	BATT 1x	BATT 2X	BATT 3X	BATT 4X	BATT 5X	BATT 6X	BATT 7X	BATT 8X	BATT 9X	BATT 10X	BATT 11X	BATT 12X	BATT 13X	BATT 14X	BATT 15X
PV 1x	0,084	0,086	0,088	0,089	0,091	0,093	0,094	0,096	0,098	0,099	0,101	0,103	0,104	0,106	0,108
PV 1,5x	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,086	0,088	0,09	0,091	0,093	0,095	0,096	0,098	0,1	0,101	0,103	0,105
PV 2x	0,086	0,086	0,086	0,086	0,087	0,087	0,088	0,09	0,092	0,093	0,095	0,097	0,098	0,1	0,102
PV2,5X	0,088	0,088	0,088	0,088	0,088	0,089	0,089	0,089	0,09	0,091	0,093	0,094	0,096	0,097	0,099
PV3X	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,092	0,092	0,093	0,094	0,095	0,097	0,099

Table 7: TCID scenario – PV+EH+TES sizing sensitivity analysis and LCOH variation

	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,08	0,08	0,081	0,081	0,082	0,082	0,082	0,083	0,083	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085	0,086	0,086
PV/EH 1,5x	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085	0,086	0,086	0,087	0,087	0,087	0,088	0,088	0,089	0,089	0,09	0,09
PV/EH 2x	0,09	0,09	0,091	0,091	0,092	0,092	0,093	0,093	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095	0,096	0,096
PV/EH 2,5X	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,101	0,101	0,102	0,102	0,103	0,103
PV/EH 3X	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106	0,107	0,107	0,108	0,108	0,109	0,109	0,11	0,11	0,11

Table 8: TCID scenario – PV+EH+TES sizing sensitivity analysis and LCOH variation with different TES CAPEX scenario

COST FUNCTION TES - 50€/kWh	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,081	0,081	0,082	0,082	0,082	0,083	0,083	0,084	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085
PV/EH 1,5x	0,084	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085	0,086	0,086	0,086	0,087	0,087	0,088	0,088	0,088	0,089	0,089
PV/EH 2x	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,091	0,091	0,092	0,092	0,092	0,093	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095
PV/EH 2,5X	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,101	0,101	0,102	0,102
PV/EH 3X	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106	0,106	0,107	0,107	0,108	0,108	0,108	0,109	0,109

COST FUNCTION TES - 40€/kWh															
	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,079	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,081	0,081	0,081	0,082	0,082	0,082	0,083	0,083	0,083	0,084	0,084
PV/EH 1,5x	0,083	0,084	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085	0,085	0,086	0,086	0,086	0,087	0,087	0,087	0,088	0,088
PV/EH 2x	0,089	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,092	0,092	0,092	0,093	0,093	0,093	0,094	0,094
PV/EH 2,5X	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,101	0,101
PV/EH 3X	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106	0,106	0,106	0,107	0,107	0,107	0,108	0,108
COST FUNCTION TES - 30€/kWh															
	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,079	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,081	0,081	0,081	0,081	0,082	0,082	0,082	0,082	0,082	0,083
PV/EH 1,5x	0,083	0,084	0,084	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085	0,085	0,085	0,086	0,086	0,086	0,086	0,087	0,087
PV/EH 2x	0,089	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,092	0,092	0,092	0,092	0,093	0,093
PV/EH 2,5X	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,099	0,099	0,1
PV/EH 3X	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106	0,106	0,106	0,107	0,107
COST FUNCTION TES - 20€/kWh															
	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,079	0,079	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,081	0,081	0,081	0,081	0,081	0,081	0,082
PV/EH 1,5x	0,083	0,083	0,084	0,084	0,084	0,084	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085	0,085	0,085	0,085	0,085	0,086
PV/EH 2x	0,089	0,089	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,092
PV/EH 2,5X	0,096	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098
PV/EH 3X	0,103	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,105	0,105	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106

Table 9: TCID scenario – PV+EH+TES sizing sensitivity analysis and LCOH variation decoupling PV/EH size

	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
EH1x-PV 1,5x	0,079	0,08	0,08	0,081	0,081	0,082	0,082	0,083	0,083	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085	0,086	0,086
EH1,5x - PV 2,25x	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095	0,096	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,101
EH2x - PV- PV 3x	0,117	0,118	0,118	0,119	0,119	0,12	0,12	0,121	0,121	0,122	0,122	0,123	0,123	0,124	0,124
EH2,5x - PV 3,75	0,148	0,148	0,149	0,149	0,15	0,15	0,151	0,151	0,152	0,152	0,153	0,153	0,154	0,154	0,155
EH3x - PV4,5X	0,185	0,185	0,186	0,186	0,187	0,187	0,188	0,188	0,189	0,189	0,19	0,19	0,191	0,191	0,192

Table 10: TCID scenario – RES Wasted [MWh_{el}] in the different scenarios

	BATT 1x	BATT 2X	BATT 3X	BATT 4X	BATT 5X	BATT 6X	BATT 7X	BATT 8X	BATT 9X	BATT 10X	BATT 11X	BATT 12X	BATT 13X	BATT 14X	BATT 15X
PV 1x	0,672075587	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PV 1,5x	1141,059193	596,062448	196,365178	16,18099655	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PV 2x	3060,736718	2393,758094	1786,454447	1251,716166	740,2157804	368,7490902	142,330769	19,39712013	0,063419419	0	0	0	0	0	0
PV2,5X	5216,391214	4530,633544	3856,713544	3205,297595	2600,490219	2045,715817	1515,929392	1014,700417	636,7674111	358,6959595	172,3855437	44,64179091	4,687379621	0	0
PV3X	7468,208704	6759,263875	6075,485064	5401,565064	4730,491241	4090,506022	3487,129555	2906,043206	2364,219294	1832,886897	1346,558878	987,9852705	778,6383006	672,9409006	591,3387
	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,5329869	219,533
PV/EH 1,5x	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2994804	329,2995
PV/EH 2x	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,0659739	439,066
PV/EH 2,5X	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8324674	548,8325
PV/EH 3X	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,5989608	658,599
	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
EH1x-PV 1,5x	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,881155	1750,88
EH1,5x - PV 2,25x	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438123	7184,438
EH2x - PV- PV 3x	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25448	16205,25
EH2,5x - PV 3,75	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,26287	2877,263
EH3x - PV4,5X	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27458	44983,27

Table 11: TCID scenario – Sensitivity analysis on the LCOH in different scenarios also considering the possibility to sell the surplus of RES to the local electric market

	BATT 1x	BATT 2X	BATT 3X	BATT 4X	BATT 5X	BATT 6X	BATT 7X	BATT 8X	BATT 9X	BATT 10X	BATT 11X	BATT 12X	BATT 13X	BATT 14X	BATT 15X
PV 1x	0,076	0,078	0,079	0,081	0,083	0,084	0,086	0,088	0,089	0,091	0,093	0,094	0,096	0,098	0,099
PV 1,5x	0,071	0,072	0,072	0,074	0,075	0,077	0,079	0,08	0,082	0,084	0,085	0,087	0,089	0,09	0,092
PV 2x	0,069	0,069	0,069	0,069	0,07	0,071	0,072	0,073	0,075	0,076	0,078	0,08	0,081	0,083	0,085
PV2,5X	0,067	0,067	0,067	0,067	0,067	0,068	0,068	0,068	0,069	0,07	0,072	0,073	0,075	0,076	0,078
PV3X	0,066	0,065	0,065	0,065	0,065	0,065	0,066	0,066	0,067	0,067	0,068	0,069	0,07	0,072	0,073
	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,079	0,08	0,08	0,081	0,081	0,082	0,082	0,082	0,083	0,083	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085	0,086
PV/EH 1,5x	0,083	0,083	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085	0,086	0,086	0,087	0,087	0,088	0,088	0,089	0,089	0,09
PV/EH 2x	0,089	0,089	0,09	0,09	0,091	0,091	0,092	0,092	0,093	0,093	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095
PV/EH 2,5X	0,095	0,096	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,101	0,101	0,102	0,102
PV/EH 3X	0,102	0,103	0,103	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106	0,107	0,107	0,108	0,108	0,109	0,109
	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
EH1x-PV 1,5x	0,076	0,076	0,077	0,077	0,078	0,078	0,079	0,079	0,079	0,08	0,08	0,081	0,081	0,082	0,082
EH1,5x - PV 2,25x	0,078	0,079	0,079	0,08	0,08	0,081	0,081	0,082	0,082	0,083	0,083	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085
EH2x - PV- PV 3x	0,082	0,083	0,083	0,084	0,084	0,085	0,085	0,086	0,086	0,087	0,087	0,088	0,088	0,089	0,089
EH2,5x - PV 3,75	0,085	0,086	0,086	0,087	0,087	0,088	0,088	0,089	0,089	0,09	0,09	0,091	0,091	0,092	0,092
EH3x - PV4,5X	0,087	0,088	0,088	0,089	0,089	0,09	0,09	0,091	0,091	0,092	0,092	0,093	0,093	0,094	0,094

4.3.2 Brick firing process

As mentioned above, the possibility of electrifying the Brick firing process by expanding the PV plant capacity and the integration of storage (BESS and TES) has been evaluated.

As in TCID side, increasing the PV size, the LCOH seems to decrease, but (at the same time) increasing the battery size (in order to maximize PV self-exploitation – Tab.18) brings to a CAPEX increase and a subsequent increase of the LCOH (Tab.14). The values show that whatever is the sizing of PV and BESS, unfortunately the LCOH EH cannot achieve the parity with LCOH NG (0.078 €/kWh_{th}).

A similar scenario occurs if considering to integrate a TES (instead of a BESS) and overscale the EH to couple it with the scale of the PV plant: despite indeed the TES has a lower CAPEX than the BESS, the increase of EH CAPEX and the need to operate it with electricity purchased from the grid, brings the two scenarios to be more or less equivalent both from the LCOH (Tab.15) and from the RES exploitation (Tab.18) point of view.

At this purpose, the possibility to further reduce the CAPEX of the TES (e.g. using ceramic production process wastes as thermal storage media) has been investigated: TES CAPEX cost function has been varied from 60 €/MWh up to 20 €/MWh. Nevertheless, no significant modifications were appreciated as in the TCID case. (Tab.16)

In order to limit the CAPEX of the “TES Scenario”, it was proposed to “decouple” the sizing of the EH and of the PV, with the PV Scale that has been considered Capacity equal to 1.5x the EH size: then the sensitivity analysis on PV/EH and TES scale have been performed. This “decoupling” has a positive effect if we look at “LCOH EH”, but it can have a negative effect in terms of RES self-exploitation and it never guarantees the parity with the baseline “LCOH NG”. (Tab. 17).

Differently than in TCID case, even considering to oversize the PV plant and enable the possibility to sell the amount of RES not fully self-exploited the LCOH cannot be comparable to the baseline NG scenario. (Tab. 19)

At the end of the analysis, looking at the different sensitivity analysis and looking for a compromise between the different KPIs analysed in the Tables presented here below, the current sizing layouts were considered as the most favourable:

- PV-BESS: PV x 2 – BESS x 3 (this variation if compared with TCID is mostly related to lower irradiation if compared with the Spanish scenario)
- PV-EH-TES: PV x 1.5 – EH x 1 – TES x 3

And such sizing will be analysed in the next paragraphs in the variation of the energy context parameters.

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Table 12: IZF scenario – PV+EH+BES sizing sensitivity analysis and LCOH variation

	LCOH IZF (NG: 0,069111111; 0,0786 with Carbon Tax)														
	BATT 1x	BATT 2X	BATT 3X	BATT 4X	BATT 5X	BATT 6X	BATT 7X	BATT 8X	BATT 9X	BATT 10X	BATT 11X	BATT 12X	BATT 13X	BATT 14X	BATT 15X
PV 1x	0,091	0,093	0,095	0,096	0,098	0,1	0,101	0,103	0,105	0,107	0,108	0,11	0,112	0,113	0,115
PV 1,5x	0,09	0,09	0,092	0,093	0,094	0,096	0,097	0,099	0,101	0,103	0,104	0,106	0,108	0,109	0,111
PV 2x	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,091	0,092	0,093	0,094	0,096	0,097	0,099	0,1	0,102	0,104	0,105	0,107
PV2,5X	0,092	0,091	0,091	0,091	0,092	0,092	0,093	0,094	0,095	0,097	0,098	0,099	0,101	0,102	0,104
PV3X	0,094	0,093	0,093	0,093	0,093	0,093	0,093	0,094	0,095	0,096	0,097	0,098	0,1	0,101	0,103

Table 13: IZF scenario – PV+EH+TES sizing sensitivity analysis and LCOH variation

	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095	0,096	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1
PV/EH 1,5x	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,101	0,101	0,102	0,102	0,103	0,103	0,104
PV/EH 2x	0,102	0,103	0,103	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106	0,107	0,107	0,107	0,108	0,108	0,109
PV/EH 2,5X	0,108	0,109	0,109	0,11	0,11	0,111	0,111	0,112	0,112	0,112	0,113	0,113	0,114	0,114	0,115
PV/EH 3X	0,115	0,115	0,116	0,116	0,117	0,117	0,117	0,118	0,118	0,119	0,119	0,12	0,12	0,121	0,121

Table 14: IZF scenario – PV+EH+TES sizing sensitivity analysis and LCOH variation with different TES CAPEX scenario

COST FUNCTION TES - 50€/kWh	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,096	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099
PV/EH 1,5x	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,101	0,101	0,101	0,102	0,102	0,103
PV/EH 2x	0,102	0,103	0,103	0,103	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106	0,107	0,107	0,107	0,108
PV/EH 2,5X	0,108	0,108	0,109	0,109	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,111	0,111	0,112	0,112	0,112	0,113	0,113	0,114
PV/EH 3X	0,115	0,115	0,115	0,116	0,116	0,117	0,117	0,117	0,118	0,118	0,119	0,119	0,119	0,12	0,12

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COST FUNCTION TES - 40€/kWh															
	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,096	0,096	0,096	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,098
PV/EH 1,5x	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,101	0,101	0,101
PV/EH 2x	0,102	0,102	0,103	0,103	0,103	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106	0,106	0,107
PV/EH 2,5X	0,108	0,108	0,109	0,109	0,109	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,111	0,111	0,111	0,112	0,112	0,112	0,112
PV/EH 3X	0,114	0,115	0,115	0,115	0,116	0,116	0,116	0,117	0,117	0,117	0,118	0,118	0,118	0,119	0,119

COST FUNCTION TES - 30€/kWh															
	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,093	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,096	0,096	0,096	0,096	0,097
PV/EH 1,5x	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,1
PV/EH 2x	0,102	0,102	0,102	0,103	0,103	0,103	0,103	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,105	0,105
PV/EH 2,5X	0,108	0,108	0,108	0,109	0,109	0,109	0,109	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,111	0,111	0,111	0,111
PV/EH 3X	0,114	0,115	0,115	0,115	0,115	0,116	0,116	0,116	0,116	0,117	0,117	0,117	0,117	0,117	0,118

COST FUNCTION TES - 20€/kWh															
	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,093	0,093	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,094	0,094	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,095
PV/EH 1,5x	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,099
PV/EH 2x	0,102	0,102	0,102	0,102	0,103	0,103	0,103	0,103	0,103	0,103	0,103	0,104	0,104	0,104	0,104
PV/EH 2,5X	0,108	0,108	0,108	0,108	0,108	0,109	0,109	0,109	0,109	0,109	0,109	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11
PV/EH 3X	0,114	0,114	0,115	0,115	0,115	0,115	0,115	0,115	0,116	0,116	0,116	0,116	0,116	0,116	0,117

Table 15: IZF scenario – PV+EH+TES sizing sensitivity analysis and LCOH variation decoupling PV/EH size

	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
EH1x-PV 1,5x	0,093	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095	0,096	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,1
EH1,5x - PV 2,25x	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106	0,107	0,107	0,108	0,108	0,109	0,109	0,11	0,11	0,111	0,111
EH2x - PV- PV 3x	0,125	0,126	0,126	0,127	0,127	0,128	0,128	0,129	0,129	0,13	0,13	0,131	0,131	0,131	0,132
EH2,5x - PV 3,75	0,154	0,155	0,155	0,156	0,156	0,157	0,157	0,158	0,158	0,159	0,159	0,16	0,16	0,161	0,161
EH3x - PV4,5X	0,191	0,192	0,192	0,192	0,193	0,193	0,194	0,194	0,195	0,195	0,196	0,196	0,197	0,197	0,198

Table 16: IZF scenario – RES Wasted [MWh_e] in the different scenarios

BESS	BATT 1x	BATT 2X	BATT 3X	BATT 4X	BATT 5X	BATT 6X	BATT 7X	BATT 8X	BATT 9X	BATT 10X	BATT 11X	BATT 12X	BATT 13X	BATT 14X	BATT 15X
PV 1x	4,41	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
PV 1,5x	454,70	275,83	158,93	52,27	1,16	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
PV 2x	1342,88	1003,79	742,01	557,34	403,02	280,68	171,72	67,02	10,34	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
PV2,5X	2453,04	2012,36	1662,15	1352,87	1098,29	885,57	717,70	567,20	441,09	325,12	226,70	137,80	97,97	62,42	43,20
PV3X	3674,45	3205,35	2768,19	2394,59	2067,78	1767,07	1511,69	1279,97	1080,43	913,65	780,97	670,25	625,36	580,92	536,48
EH-PV-TES coupled	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73	100,73
PV/EH 1,5x	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09	151,09
PV/EH 2x	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46	201,46
PV/EH 2,5X	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82	251,82
PV/EH 3X	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18	302,18
EH-PV-TES discounted	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
EH1x-PV 1,5x	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31	770,31
EH1,5x - PV 2,25x	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49	3485,49
EH2x - PV- PV 3x	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91	8346,91
EH2,5x - PV 3,75	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30	15378,30
EH3x - PV4,5X	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42	24637,42

Table 17: IZF scenario – Sensitivity analysis on the LCOH in different scenarios also considering the possibility to sell the surplus of RES to the local electric market

BESS	BATT 1x	BATT 2X	BATT 3X	BATT 4X	BATT 5X	BATT 6X	BATT 7X	BATT 8X	BATT 9X	BATT 10X	BATT 11X	BATT 12X	BATT 13X	BATT 14X	BATT 15X
PV 1x	0,091	0,093	0,095	0,096	0,098	0,1	0,101	0,103	0,105	0,107	0,108	0,11	0,112	0,113	0,115
PV 1,5x	0,089	0,09	0,091	0,093	0,094	0,096	0,097	0,099	0,101	0,103	0,104	0,106	0,108	0,109	0,111
PV 2x	0,087	0,088	0,089	0,09	0,091	0,093	0,094	0,095	0,097	0,099	0,1	0,102	0,104	0,105	0,107
PV2,5X	0,087	0,087	0,088	0,088	0,089	0,09	0,092	0,093	0,094	0,096	0,097	0,099	0,1	0,102	0,104
PV3X	0,086	0,086	0,087	0,087	0,088	0,089	0,09	0,091	0,092	0,094	0,095	0,097	0,098	0,1	0,102
EH-PV-TES coupled	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
PV/EH 1x	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095	0,096	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,099	0,1
PV/EH 1,5x	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,101	0,101	0,101	0,102	0,102	0,103	0,103
PV/EH 2x	0,102	0,102	0,103	0,103	0,104	0,104	0,105	0,105	0,106	0,106	0,107	0,107	0,108	0,108	0,108
PV/EH 2,5X	0,108	0,108	0,109	0,109	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,111	0,111	0,112	0,113	0,113	0,114	0,114
PV/EH 3X	0,114	0,114	0,115	0,115	0,116	0,116	0,117	0,117	0,118	0,118	0,119	0,119	0,12	0,12	0,121

T2.2 - Characterisation of processes energy demand and flexibility

<i>EH-PV-TES decoupled</i>	TES 1x	TES 2X	TES 3X	TES 4X	TES 5X	TES 6X	TES 7X	TES 8X	TES 9X	TES 10X	TES 11X	TES 12X	TES 13X	TES 14X	TES 15X
EH1x-PV 1,5x	0,091	0,092	0,092	0,093	0,093	0,094	0,094	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,096	0,096	0,097	0,097	0,098
EH1,5x - PV 2,25x	0,097	0,097	0,098	0,098	0,099	0,099	0,1	0,1	0,101	0,101	0,102	0,102	0,103	0,103	0,104
EH2x - PV- PV 3x	0,107	0,108	0,108	0,109	0,109	0,11	0,11	0,111	0,111	0,111	0,112	0,112	0,113	0,113	0,114
EH2,5x - PV 3,75	0,121	0,122	0,122	0,122	0,123	0,123	0,124	0,124	0,125	0,125	0,126	0,126	0,127	0,127	0,128
EH3x - PV4,5X	0,138	0,138	0,139	0,139	0,14	0,14	0,141	0,141	0,142	0,142	0,143	0,143	0,143	0,144	0,144

4.4 Assessment for the potential TCID- brick firing processes in the future energy market contexts

The analyses presented in Section 4.3 considered the current energy market conditions of each production plant (Spain for TCID, Germany for IZF) to find the optimal sizing of various technological solutions based on the integration with TES, batteries and PV. Considering the best sizing of PV+battery and of PV+TES, the energy market conditions are varied to identify which configuration might be more economically viable in the near future.

4.4.1 TCID Demosite

For the TCID production plant, the optimal configurations found in Section 4.3 were:

- PV x2 – BESS x4
- PV x1.5 – EH x1 - TES x3

Considering separately these two solutions, electricity cost, natural gas cost and carbon tax are changed simultaneously within the following ranges:

- Electric energy: 50.00-87.11 €/MWh
- Natural gas: 54.70-100.00 €/MWh
- Carbon tax: 15.00-200.00 €/t_{CO2}

LCOH_{EH} is calculated for each value of electric energy cost (it is not affected by the cost of NG and carbon tax), while LCOH_{NG} is computed for each combination of electric energy, natural gas and carbon tax. By comparing these two parameters, it is possible to identify in which cases the cost of heating would be lower electrifying the process (Figure 14). However, the installation of PV, TES and especially batteries require a significant investment. Therefore, the comparison of LCOH alone is not sufficient to evaluate the economic feasibility of each solution, and the payback period (PBP) should also be considered. PBP is a key parameter for techno-economic analysis and it represents the number of years that are required before the revenues of an investment cover its capital expenses. In this analysis, only the cases with PBP < 10 years are considered as interesting (Figure 15).

Some notable results can be observed from the analysis of LCOH and PBP. Figure 14 shows very few red cells, especially for the battery-based solution, meaning that it could

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reach a $LCOH_{EH} < LCOH_{NG}$ under small improvements of the current energy market scenario. However, the installation of a battery requires a much higher cost than a TES, leading to higher PBP. As shown in Figure 15, the TES-based solution can address this issue due to its lower CAPEX, and in many more cases a $PBP < 10$ could be achieved. For example, for an electric energy price of 80 €/MWh, the TES-based solution has a $PBP > 10$ years only in 9 out of 54 scenarios, while the battery-based solution in 28 out of 54 scenarios. This suggests that integration with TES could be a more practical way to support the early electrification of high-temperature industrial processes.

Figure 14. Variations of energy market conditions on the optimal configurations for TCID and $LCOH_{NG}$ [€/kWh]

EL. PRICE		Present Scenario											
87,11 €/MWh													
BEST BATT	LCOH	0,069 (with RES sale)											
Use D36	0,0547 €/kWh	0,065 €/kWh	0,07 €/kWh	0,08 €/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D36	LCOH	0,077 (with RES sale)				
15 €/kWh	0,0639	0,0754	0,0865	0,0921	0,1032	0,1143	15 €/kWh	0,0639	0,0754	0,0865	0,0921	0,1032	0,1143
25 €/kWh	0,0660	0,0775	0,0886	0,0942	0,1053	0,1164	25 €/kWh	0,0660	0,0775	0,0886	0,0942	0,1053	0,1164
50 €/kWh	0,0713	0,0828	0,0939	0,0994	0,1105	0,1217	50 €/kWh	0,0713	0,0828	0,0939	0,0994	0,1105	0,1217
75 €/kWh	0,0766	0,0880	0,0991	0,1047	0,1158	0,1269	75 €/kWh	0,0766	0,0880	0,0991	0,1047	0,1158	0,1269
100 €/kWh	0,0819	0,0933	0,1044	0,1100	0,1211	0,1322	100 €/kWh	0,0819	0,0933	0,1044	0,1100	0,1211	0,1322
125 €/kWh	0,0868	0,0982	0,1094	0,1149	0,1260	0,1371	125 €/kWh	0,0868	0,0986	0,1094	0,1149	0,1260	0,1371
150 €/kWh	0,0924	0,1038	0,1150	0,1205	0,1316	0,1427	150 €/kWh	0,0924	0,1038	0,1150	0,1205	0,1316	0,1427
175 €/kWh	0,0977	0,1091	0,1202	0,1258	0,1369	0,1480	175 €/kWh	0,0977	0,1091	0,1202	0,1258	0,1369	0,1480
200 €/kWh	0,1029	0,1144	0,1255	0,1310	0,1422	0,1533	200 €/kWh	0,1029	0,1144	0,1255	0,1310	0,1422	0,1533
EL. PRICE		Edit G14											
80 €/MWh													
BEST BATT	LCOH	0,066 (with RES sale)											
Use D36	0,0547 €/kWh	0,065 €/kWh	0,07 €/kWh	0,08 €/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D36	LCOH	0,072 (with RES sale)				
15 €/kWh	0,0639	0,0754	0,0865	0,0921	0,1032	0,1143	15 €/kWh	0,0639	0,0754	0,0865	0,0921	0,1032	0,1143
25 €/kWh	0,0660	0,0775	0,0886	0,0942	0,1053	0,1164	25 €/kWh	0,0660	0,0775	0,0886	0,0942	0,1053	0,1164
50 €/kWh	0,0713	0,0828	0,0939	0,0994	0,1105	0,1217	50 €/kWh	0,0713	0,0828	0,0939	0,0994	0,1105	0,1217
75 €/kWh	0,0766	0,0880	0,0991	0,1047	0,1158	0,1269	75 €/kWh	0,0766	0,0880	0,0991	0,1047	0,1158	0,1269
100 €/kWh	0,0819	0,0933	0,1044	0,1100	0,1211	0,1322	100 €/kWh	0,0819	0,0933	0,1044	0,1100	0,1211	0,1322
125 €/kWh	0,0868	0,0982	0,1094	0,1149	0,1260	0,1371	125 €/kWh	0,0868	0,0986	0,1094	0,1149	0,1260	0,1371
150 €/kWh	0,0924	0,1038	0,1150	0,1205	0,1316	0,1427	150 €/kWh	0,0924	0,1038	0,1150	0,1205	0,1316	0,1427
175 €/kWh	0,0977	0,1091	0,1202	0,1258	0,1369	0,1480	175 €/kWh	0,0977	0,1091	0,1202	0,1258	0,1369	0,1480
200 €/kWh	0,1029	0,1144	0,1255	0,1310	0,1422	0,1533	200 €/kWh	0,1029	0,1144	0,1255	0,1310	0,1422	0,1533
EL. PRICE		Edit G14											
70 €/MWh													
BEST BATT	LCOH	0,061 (with RES sale)											
Use D36	0,0547 €/kWh	0,065 €/kWh	0,07 €/kWh	0,08 €/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D36	LCOH	0,065 (with RES sale)				
15 €/kWh	0,0639	0,0754	0,0865	0,0921	0,1032	0,1143	15 €/kWh	0,0639	0,0754	0,0865	0,0921	0,1032	0,1143
25 €/kWh	0,0660	0,0775	0,0886	0,0942	0,1053	0,1164	25 €/kWh	0,0660	0,0775	0,0886	0,0942	0,1053	0,1164
50 €/kWh	0,0713	0,0828	0,0939	0,0994	0,1105	0,1217	50 €/kWh	0,0713	0,0828	0,0939	0,0994	0,1105	0,1217
75 €/kWh	0,0766	0,0880	0,0991	0,1047	0,1158	0,1269	75 €/kWh	0,0766	0,0880	0,0991	0,1047	0,1158	0,1269
100 €/kWh	0,0819	0,0933	0,1044	0,1100	0,1211	0,1322	100 €/kWh	0,0819	0,0933	0,1044	0,1100	0,1211	0,1322
125 €/kWh	0,0868	0,0982	0,1094	0,1149	0,1260	0,1371	125 €/kWh	0,0868	0,0986	0,1094	0,1149	0,1260	0,1371
150 €/kWh	0,0924	0,1038	0,1150	0,1205	0,1316	0,1427	150 €/kWh	0,0924	0,1038	0,1150	0,1205	0,1316	0,1427
175 €/kWh	0,0977	0,1091	0,1202	0,1258	0,1369	0,1480	175 €/kWh	0,0977	0,1091	0,1202	0,1258	0,1369	0,1480
200 €/kWh	0,1029	0,1144	0,1255	0,1310	0,1422	0,1533	200 €/kWh	0,1029	0,1144	0,1255	0,1310	0,1422	0,1533

- In red, where electrification is not economically viable.
- In yellow, costs of NG and carbon tax that lead to the same $LCOH_{NG}$ and $LCOH_{EH}$ for the baseline configuration (no TES or battery, only pre-installed PV).

Figure 15. Variations of energy market conditions on the optimal configurations for TCID and PBP [years]

EL. PRICE		Present Scenario											
87,11 €/MWh													
BEST BATT LCOH		0,069 (with RES safe)					BEST TES LCOH		0,077 (with RES safe)				
Use D39	0,0547 €/kWh	0,065 €/kWh	0,07 €/kWh	0,08 €/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D39	0,0547 €/kWh	0,065 €/kWh	0,07 €/kWh	0,08 €/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh
15 €/tCO2		73.0908	37.7661	19.2038	12.8754	9.6841	15 €/tCO2		14.9951	9.6043	5.5871	3.9394	
25 €/tCO2		53.9465	22.6597	17.5659	12.1179	9.2492	25 €/tCO2		165.9268	12.3624	8.4515	5.1764	3.7307
50 €/tCO2	231.8606	32.5997	17.7716	14.4788	10.5640	8.3156	50 €/tCO2		24.0783	8.5914	6.5008	4.3727	3.2943
75 €/tCO2	60.7860	23.3572	14.6182	12.3145	9.3634	7.5532	75 €/tCO2		12.9810	6.5833	5.2818	3.7851	2.9493
100 €/tCO2	34.9780	18.1978	12.4153	10.7132	8.4078	6.9189	100 €/tCO2	28.2244	8.8857	5.3361	4.4477	3.3367	2.6698
125 €/tCO2	25.0156	15.0745	10.8777	9.5485	7.6732	6.4137	125 €/tCO2	14.5490	6.8567	4.5309	3.8739	3.0030	2.4518
150 €/tCO2	18.9158	12.6218	9.5399	8.5020	6.9826	5.9239	150 €/tCO2	9.3950	5.4481	3.8698	3.3802	2.6975	2.2443
175 €/tCO2	15.3837	10.9450	8.5499	7.7067	6.4370	5.5265	175 €/tCO2	7.0451	4.5651	3.4023	3.0180	2.4618	2.0787
200 €/tCO2	12.9631	9.6614	7.7460	7.0474	5.9705	5.1791	200 €/tCO2	5.6355	3.9284	3.0356	2.7259	2.2639	1.9358

EL. PRICE		Edit G14											
80 €/MWh													
BEST BATT LCOH		0,066 (with RES safe)					BEST TES LCOH		0,072 (with RES safe)				
Use D39	0,0547 €/kWh	0,065 €/kWh	0,07 €/kWh	0,08 €/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D39	0,0547 €/kWh	0,065 €/kWh	0,07 €/kWh	0,08 €/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh
15 €/tCO2		45.4777	21.0158	16.5617	11.6313	8.9631	15 €/tCO2		41.9492	10.1315	7.3457	4.7394	3.4982
25 €/tCO2	2075.0493	37.2521	19.0700	15.3290	11.0096	8.5893	25 €/tCO2		26.2880	8.8571	6.6518	4.4405	3.3326
50 €/tCO2	79.2384	25.6527	15.4855	12.9243	9.7117	7.7783	50 €/tCO2		13.5972	6.7382	5.3810	3.8358	2.9800
75 €/tCO2	40.3904	19.5616	13.0353	11.1717	8.6876	7.1073	75 €/tCO2	31.3093	9.1702	5.4374	4.5178	3.3760	2.6949
100 €/tCO2	27.1028	15.8081	11.2545	9.8377	7.8589	6.5428	100 €/tCO2	14.8272	6.9179	4.5575	3.8933	3.0147	2.4596
125 €/tCO2	20.3937	13.2631	9.9018	8.7882	7.1745	6.0614	125 €/tCO2	9.9259	5.6225	3.9569	3.4465	2.7396	2.2734
150 €/tCO2	16.3471	11.4240	8.8394	7.9411	6.5997	5.6460	150 €/tCO2	7.2227	4.6390	3.4432	3.0501	2.4831	2.0939
175 €/tCO2	13.6405	10.0328	7.9829	7.2430	6.1103	5.2839	175 €/tCO2	5.7485	3.9830	3.0681	2.7521	2.2819	1.9490
200 €/tCO2	11.7028	8.9436	7.2777	6.6576	5.6884	4.9654	200 €/tCO2	4.7742	3.4895	2.7668	2.5071	2.1109	1.8228

EL. PRICE		Edit G14													
70 €/MWh															
BEST BATT LCOH		0,061 (with RES safe)					BEST TES LCOH		0,065 (with RES safe)						
Use D39	0,0547 €/kWh	0,065 €/kWh	0,07 €/kWh	0,08 €/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D39	0,0547 €/kWh	0,065 €/kWh	0,07 €/kWh	0,08 €/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh		
15 €/tCO2		136.7904	29.6977	16.8728	13.8765	10.2398	8.1134	15 €/tCO2		14.5213	6.9576	5.5200	3.9059	3.0222	
25 €/tCO2		82.1980	25.9552	15.5952	13.0006	9.7548	7.8059	25 €/tCO2		167.8865	12.0386	6.3319	5.1187	3.7006	2.8978
50 €/tCO2		41.1455	19.7370	13.1129	11.2287	8.7220	7.1303	50 €/tCO2		24.1192	8.4338	5.1697	4.3315	3.2709	2.6275
75 €/tCO2		27.4407	15.9225	11.3124	9.8818	7.8870	6.5623	75 €/tCO2		12.9929	6.4904	4.3680	3.7542	2.9305	2.4033
100 €/tCO2		20.5844	13.3436	9.9466	8.8235	7.1979	6.0782	100 €/tCO2		8.8913	5.2748	3.7815	3.3126	2.6544	2.2143
125 €/tCO2		16.6761	11.5837	8.9347	8.0180	6.6527	5.6848	125 €/tCO2		6.8600	4.4867	3.3586	2.9835	2.4388	2.0623
150 €/tCO2		13.7255	10.0787	8.0120	7.2669	6.1273	5.2966	150 €/tCO2		5.4502	3.8375	2.9811	2.6818	2.2334	1.9135
175 €/tCO2		11.7654	8.9801	7.3018	6.6779	5.7031	4.9767	175 €/tCO2		4.5666	3.3773	2.6957	2.4487	2.0693	1.7917
200 €/tCO2		10.2951	8.0975	6.7074	6.1771	5.3339	4.6932	200 €/tCO2		3.9295	3.0157	2.4603	2.2528	1.9277	1.6846

- In bright green, where PBP < 10 years for the considered electrified solution, in light green where it is about 10 years.
- In yellow, costs of NG and carbon tax that lead to the same LCOHNG and LCOHEH for the baseline configuration (no TES or battery, only pre-installed PV).

4.4.2 Brick firing process

For the brick firing process, the optimal configurations found in Section 4.3 were:

- PV x2 – BESS x3
- PV x1.5 - EH x1 – TES x3

Considering separately these two solutions, electricity cost, natural gas cost and carbon tax are changed simultaneously within the following ranges:

- Electric energy: 60.00-95.04 €/MWh
- Natural gas: 62.20-100.00 €/MWh
- Carbon tax: 45.00-200.00 €/tCO2

Co-funded by the European Union.

Similarly to the analysis presented in Section 4.4.1 for TCID, $LCOH_{EH}$ is computed for each value of electric energy cost (it is not affected by the cost of NG and carbon tax), while $LCOH_{NG}$ is computed for each combination of electric energy, natural gas and carbon tax. By comparing these two parameters, it is possible to identify in which cases the cost of heating would be lower electrifying the process (Figure 16). However, the installation of PV, TES and especially batteries requires a significant investment. Therefore, the comparison of LCOH alone is not sufficient to evaluate the economic feasibility of each solution, and the payback period (PBP) should be considered as well. In this analysis, only the cases with $PBP < 10$ years are considered as interesting (Figure 17).

Some interesting results can be derived from the observation of LCOH and PBP. Figure 16 shows very few red cells, especially for the battery-based solution, meaning that it could reach a $LCOH_{EH} < LCOH_{NG}$ under small improvements of the current energy market scenario. However, the installation of a battery requires a much higher cost than a TES, leading to higher PBPs. As shown in Figure 17, the TES-based solution can overcome this issue thanks to its lower CAPEX, and in many more cases a $PBP < 10$ could be achieved. For example, for an electric energy price of 90 €/MWh, the TES-based solution has a $PBP > 10$ years only in 10 out of 48 scenarios, while the battery-based solution in 36 out of 48 scenarios. This suggests that, also for IZF, integration with TES could be a more viable way to facilitate the early electrification of high-temperature industrial processes.

Comparing these results with the ones obtained in Section 4.4.1, the Spanish energy market scenario seems slightly more favourable, especially for the adoption of batteries. However, this also depends on the specific characteristic of the two plants considered (energy demand, pre-existing PV, etc.), and cannot be easily generalized without further investigation.

In general, similar conclusions can be drawn from the two case studies. It appears evident that the economic feasibility of electrification will be achievable if the energy markets of Germany and Spain evolve towards electricity and gas prices that are significantly different from the current levels. The increase in carbon taxes alone is unlikely to achieve this goal, but it can be a useful tool to facilitate the transition towards electrified high-temperature processes.

Figure 16. Variations of energy market conditions on the optimal configurations for IZF and LCOH_{NG} [€/kWh].

EL. PRICE	95,04 €/MWh	Present Scenario									
BEST BATT	LCOH					LCOH					
	0,089 (with RES sale)					0,091 (with RES sale)					
Use D36	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D36	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh
45 €/tCO2	0.0786	0.0873	0.1050	0.1095	0.1206	45 €/tCO2	0.0786	0.0873	0.1050	0.1095	0.1206
50 €/tCO2	0.0797	0.0883	0.1061	0.1105	0.1217	50 €/tCO2	0.0797	0.0883	0.1061	0.1105	0.1217
75 €/tCO2	0.0849	0.0936	0.1114	0.1158	0.1269	75 €/tCO2	0.0849	0.0936	0.1114	0.1158	0.1269
100 €/tCO2	0.0902	0.0989	0.1166	0.1211	0.1322	100 €/tCO2	0.0902	0.0989	0.1166	0.1211	0.1322
125 €/tCO2	0.0958	0.1044	0.1222	0.1267	0.1378	125 €/tCO2	0.0958	0.1044	0.1222	0.1267	0.1378
150 €/tCO2	0.1007	0.1094	0.1272	0.1316	0.1427	150 €/tCO2	0.1007	0.1094	0.1272	0.1316	0.1427
175 €/tCO2	0.1060	0.1147	0.1324	0.1369	0.1480	175 €/tCO2	0.1060	0.1147	0.1324	0.1369	0.1480
200 €/tCO2	0.1113	0.1199	0.1377	0.1422	0.1533	200 €/tCO2	0.1113	0.1199	0.1377	0.1422	0.1533
EL. PRICE	90€/MWh	Edit G14									
BEST BATT	LCOH					LCOH					
	0,086 (with RES sale)					0,087 (with RES sale)					
Use D36	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D36	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh
45 €/tCO2	0.0786	0.0873	0.1050	0.1095	0.1206	45 €/tCO2	0.0786	0.0873	0.1050	0.1095	0.1206
50 €/tCO2	0.0797	0.0883	0.1061	0.1105	0.1217	50 €/tCO2	0.0797	0.0883	0.1061	0.1105	0.1217
75 €/tCO2	0.0849	0.0936	0.1114	0.1158	0.1269	75 €/tCO2	0.0849	0.0936	0.1114	0.1158	0.1269
100 €/tCO2	0.0902	0.0989	0.1166	0.1211	0.1322	100 €/tCO2	0.0902	0.0989	0.1166	0.1211	0.1322
125 €/tCO2	0.0958	0.1044	0.1222	0.1267	0.1378	125 €/tCO2	0.0958	0.1044	0.1222	0.1267	0.1378
150 €/tCO2	0.1007	0.1094	0.1272	0.1316	0.1427	150 €/tCO2	0.1007	0.1094	0.1272	0.1316	0.1427
175 €/tCO2	0.1060	0.1147	0.1324	0.1369	0.1480	175 €/tCO2	0.1060	0.1147	0.1324	0.1369	0.1480
200 €/tCO2	0.1113	0.1199	0.1377	0.1422	0.1533	200 €/tCO2	0.1113	0.1199	0.1377	0.1422	0.1533
EL. PRICE	80€/MWh	Edit G14									
BEST BATT	LCOH					LCOH					
	0,079 (with RES sale)					0,08 (with RES sale)					
Use D36	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D36	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh
45 €/tCO2	0.0786	0.0873	0.1050	0.1095	0.1206	45 €/tCO2	0.0786	0.0873	0.1050	0.1095	0.1206
50 €/tCO2	0.0797	0.0883	0.1061	0.1105	0.1217	50 €/tCO2	0.0797	0.0883	0.1061	0.1105	0.1217
75 €/tCO2	0.0849	0.0936	0.1114	0.1158	0.1269	75 €/tCO2	0.0849	0.0936	0.1114	0.1158	0.1269
100 €/tCO2	0.0902	0.0989	0.1166	0.1211	0.1322	100 €/tCO2	0.0902	0.0989	0.1166	0.1211	0.1322
125 €/tCO2	0.0958	0.1044	0.1222	0.1267	0.1378	125 €/tCO2	0.0958	0.1044	0.1222	0.1267	0.1378
150 €/tCO2	0.1007	0.1094	0.1272	0.1316	0.1427	150 €/tCO2	0.1007	0.1094	0.1272	0.1316	0.1427
175 €/tCO2	0.1060	0.1147	0.1324	0.1369	0.1480	175 €/tCO2	0.1060	0.1147	0.1324	0.1369	0.1480
200 €/tCO2	0.1113	0.1199	0.1377	0.1422	0.1533	200 €/tCO2	0.1113	0.1199	0.1377	0.1422	0.1533

- In red, where electrification is not economically viable.
- In yellow, costs of NG and carbon tax that lead to the same LCOH_{NG} and LCOH_{EH} for the baseline configuration (no TES or battery, only pre-installed PV).

Co-funded by the European Union.

Figure 17. Variations of energy market conditions on the optimal configurations for IZF and PBP [years].

EL PRICE	95,04 €/MWh	Present Scenario									
BEST BATT	LCOH	0,089 (with RES sale)					BEST TES	LCOH	0,091 (with RES sale)		
Use D39	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D39	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh
45 €/tCO2			26.4371	20.7329	13.4681	45 €/tCO2		11.4999	8.5541	5.2147	
50 €/tCO2			24.8179	19.7238	13.0348	50 €/tCO2		10.6317	8.0643	5.0285	
75 €/tCO2		90.8704	18.9998	15.8632	11.2289	75 €/tCO2	102.2449	7.7183	6.2693	4.2667	
100 €/tCO2	327.8645	42.8386	15.3915	13.2665	9.8624	100 €/tCO2	22.0824	6.0582	5.1279	3.7054	
125 €/tCO2	61.9997	27.4555	12.8123	11.3049	8.7356	125 €/tCO2	40.7733	12.0599	4.9334	4.2984	3.2519
150 €/tCO2	36.0652	20.8242	11.1547	9.9945	7.9319	150 €/tCO2	17.2712	8.5989	4.2359	3.7591	2.9335
175 €/tCO2	24.9586	16.5673	9.8052	8.8973	7.2248	175 €/tCO2	10.7061	6.5877	3.6822	3.3165	2.6568
200 €/tCO2	19.0821	13.7555	8.7469	8.0171	6.6335	200 €/tCO2	7.7574	5.3390	3.2564	2.9671	2.4278
EL PRICE	90€/MWh	Edit G14									
BEST BATT	LCOH	0,086 (with RES sale)					BEST TES	LCOH	0,087 (with RES sale)		
Use D39	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D39	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh
45 €/tCO2		248.9051	21.9082	17.8406	12.1848	45 €/tCO2		8.8852	7.0179	4.6007	
50 €/tCO2		154.1938	20.7845	17.0883	11.8292	50 €/tCO2		8.3578	6.6848	4.4552	
75 €/tCO2		53.1234	16.5422	14.1126	10.3225	75 €/tCO2	28.2721	6.4453	5.4025	3.8467	
100 €/tCO2		53.1234	16.5422	14.1126	10.3225	100 €/tCO2	80.1202	14.1094	5.2450	4.5330	3.3845
125 €/tCO2	41.7562	22.6030	11.6456	10.3868	8.1771	125 €/tCO2	19.9537	9.2158	4.3804	3.8724	3.0021
150 €/tCO2	28.1318	17.9082	10.2598	9.2700	7.4687	150 €/tCO2	11.9775	7.0480	3.8217	3.4292	2.7287
175 €/tCO2	20.8831	14.6673	9.1069	8.3185	6.8385	175 €/tCO2	8.4038	5.6374	3.3651	3.0570	2.4877
200 €/tCO2	16.6046	12.4196	8.1870	7.5442	6.3064	200 €/tCO2	6.4725	4.6972	3.0059	2.7577	2.2858
EL PRICE	80€/MWh	Edit G14									
BEST BATT	LCOH	0,079 (with RES sale)					BEST TES	LCOH	0,08 (with RES sale)		
Use D39	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh	Use D39	0,0622 €/kWh	0,07€/kWh	0,086€/kWh	0,09 €/kWh	0,10 €/kWh
45 €/tCO2		51.1973	16.3506	13.9730	10.2476	45 €/tCO2		22.9678	6.1229	5.1742	3.7295
50 €/tCO2	585.9452	45.4545	15.7165	13.5072	9.9948	50 €/tCO2		19.7472	5.8678	4.9908	3.6333
75 €/tCO2	71.1977	29.1216	13.1637	11.5777	8.8976	75 €/tCO2	36.0350	11.6084	4.8561	4.2396	3.2182
100 €/tCO2	37.9015	21.4236	11.3244	10.1305	8.0174	100 €/tCO2	15.8090	8.2204	4.1420	3.6849	2.8882
125 €/tCO2	25.3401	16.7345	9.8635	8.9453	7.2565	125 €/tCO2	9.9118	6.2781	3.5834	3.2361	2.6050
150 €/tCO2	19.5842	14.0144	8.8509	8.1044	6.6931	150 €/tCO2	7.4480	5.1906	3.2006	2.9207	2.3967
175 €/tCO2	15.7728	11.9483	7.9795	7.3677	6.1826	175 €/tCO2	5.8904	4.3828	2.8740	2.6463	2.2087
200 €/tCO2	13.2032	10.4131	7.2643	6.7537	5.7444	200 €/tCO2	4.8716	3.7927	2.6079	2.4190	2.0481

- In bright green, where PBP < 10 years for the considered electrified solution.
- In light green, where it is about 10 years, in yellow costs of NG and carbon tax that lead to the same LCOHNG and LCOHEH for the baseline configuration (no TES or battery, only pre-installed PV).

5 Flexibility potential in eLITHE new electrified process.

New processes in eLITHE are focused on process electrification and are designed to offer several clear advantages over the current energy characterization profiles described in this document, namely energy efficiency and energy flexibility. It is indeed too early at this point to assess the real flexibility potential of the new processes. In terms of process-driven flexibility and energy storage, possibilities are rather limited but the sources identified in chapter 3 for the current process are still valid in general for the new processes.

Electrification creates the opportunity of higher electricity consumption and increases the potential for renewable energy generation capacity to feed the new process energy demands and the currently low energy self-sufficiency. The new generation capacity would provide higher energy flexibility as a new energy source would be added or enhanced. Consequently, a higher generation capacity would allow for further energy storage that would entail a valuable short-term flexibility vector to be used both internally and externally. In summary, investment in new generation and storage capacity is highly encouraged in the demonstration industries, and in all industries working to electrify their production processes.

A possible flexibility source for the electricity demand derived from the electrification of the thermal processes can be obtained from those processes that combine the use of traditional fuel burning and the electric heating technology selected for every industry. This is the case of the frits melting, that intend to include a small gas burner to support the process start up, and the bricks firing, with CO₂-free hydrogen burning in parallel to the electric system. This dual thermal process enables the simultaneous use of either energy carrier and the consumption rate of one vector should be balanced by the other. In this sense, an electricity upwards flexibility can be attained by a higher gas contribution whereas, conversely, downwards flexibility can be achieved by reducing gas usage. The implementation of this promising flexibility source is not costless as a dual system has to be catered for, however this is the default path forward in most of the demonstrators. In addition, the flexibility is not expected to be unlimited, and testing should be carried out as to identify the limitations of this dual process. The use of this flexibility will be determined by the costs of using either technology and the expected economic benefits of flexibility exploitation. The eLITHE decision support tool to be developed in WP3 should help calculate these costs and benefits to assist the user to make the optimal decision at each case based on process and market requirements and inputs.

A preliminary analysis carried out with the first inputs of the new process designers on each individual process of the demonstration industries draw the following conclusions:

- Frits melting process: The selected technologies are direct resistive heating of the liquified ceramic material inside the smelter along with inductive heating at the outlet

to assure fluidity. The ambition of the lab prototype and the industrial prototype is to run only on electricity in the steady phase of the process. However, a small gas burner is required to start the process as the raw material is dielectric. This gas burner would only be used at the start-up of every new batch where the intake of raw material is in solid state until the material mix in the furnace reaches the liquid state. The proposal that is made is to eventually keep using a fraction of thermal energy produced by gas burning when electricity flexibility is required and economically interesting. If the process runs in full electric mode, no or little downwards flexibility is then expected.

- Brick firing process: the selected electric heating technology is electric resistance heating of the brick material. However new process designers are relying on a dual strategy combining this technology with green hydrogen burning at variable rates. This combustion does not produce CO₂. Thus, the hybrid usage of the dual energy source usage of the new brick firing process could provide electricity flexibility in both directions, upwards and downwards by shifting the mix of H₂ combustion and electric heating. However, testing is needed to confirm this possibility and find out the limits of the flexibility to be used.
- Alumina calcination process: The new electric process will run fully on microwave technology. As the power of the commercially available magnetrons is limited, the design will consider maximizing efficiency for the most cost-effective power available. Hybrid operation is not currently considered in the design of the new process. The use of this dual system operation is then discarded in the new alumina calcination process.

The hybrid thermal processes will be closely monitored before initiating the design of the Decision Support System (DSS) tool to allow for a full exploitation of hybrid processes in the two demonstrators featuring dual energy carriers (frits melting and brick firing).

6 Conclusions

eLITHE's deliverable D2.2 makes a full energy characterization of the three demonstration industries focusing on the current thermal processes, all based on natural gas burning: frits melting, brick firing and alumina calcination. The characterization includes the description of the main equipment (kilns), the electricity and gas demands per ton of output, the involved ancillary equipment (dryers, preheaters ...) and the generation assets in place. The main objective is to establish models to predict the energy consumption per unit of the reference product in each process, serving as a baseline to compare the impact of the new developments within the project. The energy characterization was conducted using historical data on energy consumption and production. Throughout the process, clear objectives were defined, and the scope was narrowed to ensure the representativeness of the analysis, covering everything from the selection of the reference product and equipment to the collection and analysis of energy and production data. Furthermore, data request templates were designed for each process, requesting key information about production, energy carriers, tariffs, and process control parameters.

A demand baseline of the current process has been formulated to serve as a comparison with the new envisaged process changes and equipment aimed at electrifying the thermal processes. The analysis reveals the most relevant energy drivers. These baselines are validated for the reference product and equipment chosen at each demonstrator and use the output production as independent variable. They provide a crucial reference framework for the future assessment of the technological advancements in the project. Electrification also opens the door to broader self-consumption of self-generated energy and storage solutions, giving room to larger PV and BES facilities on site.

The second main objective of this deliverable is the development and application of a suitable methodology to identify and assess the potential energy flexibility from three perspectives: process, energy carrier and energy storage. This flexibility potential is assessed and quantified wherever possible and is intended to guide the Decision Support System (DSS) being developed within eLITHE to support the elicitation and delivery of electricity flexibility both implicitly and explicitly. Due to product quality constraints, the process flexibility has little margin to play with. However, there is a significant potential in energy storage and the hybrid use of simultaneous energy carriers.

The analysis of remuneration focused on understanding how the integration with power generation systems and storages could help to overcome the electrification economic feasibility in the three demonstration industries. Photovoltaic technology was considered for self-production of electricity, given the fact that PV facilities already exist at the ceramic and brick manufacturing sites.

The techno-economic performance of the frits and brick production plants was analysed over a year, considering different sizes of PV, TES (thermal energy storage) and BES (battery energy storage), in order to find a configuration characterized both by low LCOH (levelized cost of heat) and limited capital costs. To do this, a simple but robust energy management algorithm was implemented to determine PV production and energy exchanges with TES, BES and the electricity grid on an hourly basis. The best solutions for PV+TES and PV+BES were then selected and analysed referring to different energy market scenarios (costs of gas, electricity and carbon taxes).

This study showed better results in terms of LCOH for the BES-based solutions, with values of $LCOH_{EH}$ (with electric heater) lower than $LCOH_{NG}$ (with natural gas) that could be reached with minimum changes in the current energy market. However, considering also the return of investment to assess the economic performance of the two configurations, TES integration appears to be a more feasible solution. In fact, BES have a much higher CAPEX (capital expenses) than TES, and a payback below 10 years could be reached only under significant variations of the market. On the other hand, the lower cost of TES is beneficial for the payback, despite their higher cost of heat (LCOH). Thus, integration with PV and TES appears to be the most promising solution for economically viable electrified processes in the near future.

The results of this deliverable will enable the fair assessment of gains and advantages of the new electric processes and will set the basis of the Decision Support and Market Flexibility Tools that will enable economic savings and the contribution of energy-intensive industries in the demand flexibility markets of the close future.

7 References

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